

PRECINCT

Preparedness and Resilience Enforcement for Critical Infrastructure Cascading Cyber-Physical Threats

D6.1 PRECINCT CyberPhysical Security Stakeholder Needs Knowledge Base - Liaison and cooperation

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Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

Abbreviation / Term	Description
CEN-CENELEC	The European Committee for Standardization - the European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization
CI	Critical Infrastructure
CIP	Critical Infrastructure Protection
EU	European Union
ECSCI	European Cluster for Securing Critical Infrastructure
GA	Grant Agreement
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
SEW	Stakeholder Engagement Workshop
LEAs	Law Enforcement Agencies
LL	Living Labs
SEW	Stakeholder Engagement Workshop
WP	Work Package

1 Executive Summary

This deliverable describes the activities carried out by the various PRECINCT partners in regards to PRECINCT's CyberPhysical Security Stakeholder Needs Knowledge Base, as well as all liaison and cooperation activities undertaken throughout the project.

The report starts by describing the context of PRECINCTs Stakeholder Landscape, followed by the activities that PRECINCT partners undertook to engage with said stakeholders and provide them with knowledge created within the project. Additionally, the forums in which this knowledge is hosted, also known as. the Stakeholder Needs Knowledge Base, is described in full detail.

The complementary actions of liaison and cooperation activities which furthered the outreach of PRECINCT are also outlined. Eventually, the deliverable concludes by assessing whether its goals were reached. In this case, the assessment determined that PRECINCT met its objective of sharing the project findings to a large group of relevant Critical Infrastructure (CI) stakeholders across the EU.

2 Introduction

Stakeholders play a vital role in research projects as they help to define the user needs, validate results, and in many cases they are the end-users of the developed solution developed, among other things. In order to maximise the impact of PRECINCT towards its stakeholders and vice versa, the project worked on developing a Stakeholder Needs Knowledge Base, which allows stakeholders to learn and benefit from the knowledge created by the project. Over the course of two years, PRECINCT partners undertook many outreach activities, as well, to interact with industry CI stakeholders, through organizing its own events, attending external events, publishing various materials and more in order to create the Stakeholder Needs Knowledge Base. The current deliverable aims to outline these activities, describe the Stakeholder Needs Knowledge Base for stakeholders and define the project's stakeholders. In addition, the document describes the liaison and cooperation activities of PRECINCT throughout the project's lifespan, which complimented the stakeholder activities and boosted the outreach of the project.

2.1 Mapping PRECINCT Outputs

This section aims at mapping PRECINCT's Grant Agreement (GA) commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and respective Task description, against the project's outputs and work performed.

Table 1 : Adherence to PRECINCT's GA, Deliverables and Task descriptions

PRECINCT GA Component Title	PRECINCT GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			
<i>D6.1</i>	PRECINCT Cyber-Physical Security Stakeholder Needs Knowledge Base - Liaison and cooperation (R, PU, M24) (EOS) Stakeholder workshops, Collaboration meetings and commercial event report.	<i>Chapter 4; Chapter 5; Chapter 6</i>	These chapters report the activities undertaken during the PRECINCT events and discuss the Stakeholder Needs Knowledge Base

TASKS			
<p>76.1 PRECINCT Cyber-Physical Security Stakeholder Needs Knowledge Base - Liaison and cooperation</p>	<p>This task will guide PRECINCT’s awareness events, knowledge base and open access library with the central goal of sharing the project findings to a large and relevant CI stakeholders across EU.</p> <p>Our aim is to consolidate and present the main outputs of PRECINCT and to ensure a strong interaction with industry CI stakeholders, end-users, citizens, solutions providers, and broad CI academia interest groups.</p> <p>Two prominent stakeholder workshops will be organised in Brussels in M7, M14.</p> <p>Clustering activities with other relevant EU CI projects to ensure synergies will is also planned.</p> <p>This task will also take care of the organization of a commercial event (final event of the project) where all open tools and assets will be presented to a broad CI audience at M24.</p>	<p><i>Chapter 4; Chapter 5; Chapter 6</i></p> <p><i>Chapter 3; Chapter 4; Chapter 5</i></p> <p><i>Chapter 4</i></p> <p><i>Chapter 5</i></p> <p><i>Chapter 4</i></p>	

2.2 Document Overview and Report Structure

As mentioned above, the document reports all actions and activities carried out during the course of the PRECINCT project undertaken in its Task 6.1 – “CyberPhysical Security Stakeholder Needs Knowledge Base, Liaison and cooperation”. In addition, an assessment for each activity is conducted to determine whether the actions were sufficient in reaching the goals or objectives outlined in the GA. The document is structured as follows:

- Chapter 3 defines the PRECINCT stakeholders, and the PRECINCT stakeholder landscape. In addition, it describes how PRECINCT identified and chose the stakeholders invited to events, demos, and sent dissemination materials.
- Chapter 4 covers the 4 PRECINCT-led events that were part of the core of T6.1. After describing each event and their objectives, it is further assessed if the events were successful, not only in execution but also in furthering the Stakeholder Needs Knowledge Base and liaison and cooperation tasks.
- Chapter 5 covers the liaison and cooperation tasks under the project.
- Chapter 6 discusses the actual output of T6.1, i.e., the knowledge base itself. The knowledge base consists of three parts. The section describes each of the three parts respectively. Afterwards, a general assessment of the knowledge base is conducted and presented.
- Finally, Chapter 7 concludes the document with some observations regarding the overall assessment of the task and lessons learned.

3 PRECINCT Stakeholder Landscape

The PRECINCT stakeholders are simply defined as the entities/parties that could or will be affected by the work of the PRECINCT project and are or could be interested in the outcome of the project. They were first identified in the early stages of the project. The stakeholders were depicted in the GA, as seen in the figure below, and constitute First Responders, Critical Infrastructure Operators, Industry & Technology Providers, Standardization Bodies, Policy & Decision-makers, Academia & Research and other relevant networks and Citizens.

Figure 3-1: PRECINCT Stakeholders

First responders are identified as one of the key stakeholders for the PRECINCT ecosystem due to the role they play as the initial actors in the event of a CI failure. By inviting them to stakeholder workshops and identifying their needs and collecting feedback on tools (e.g., cyber-physical security management platform), PRECINCT Partners could ensure the tools were relevant and increase the chance of successful uptake. To further enhance PRECINCT's impact and relevance, it was important to engage with stakeholders at all levels; therefore, there were first responders targeted at the local level, national level, and European level. The same approach followed for all stakeholder groups as well. **Critical Infrastructure Operators** are vitally important to the PRECINCT project, considered as the end-users of the technologies provided by PRECINCT and will benefit by early identification of potential cascading effects among different infrastructures. Since there are mostly national Critical Infrastructure Operators, they represent the main entities targeted by PRECINCT. Nevertheless, whenever possible, local level entities were also contacted together with European associations that represented the CI Operators. **Industry & technology providers** and **Academia & Research** as stakeholders worked together with the PRECINCT partners to further develop the technological aspects of the project (e.g., modelling simulation), communicate their needs and feedback at PRECINCT events, and maximise exploitation. **Policy makers, decision makers and Standards Developing Organisations** would mainly be concerned with the policy recommendations and standardization tasks in the PRECINCT project, benefitting from recommendations representing an actual picture of the potential cascading effects and how to minimise their occurrence and damages through policy changes and standardization opportunities. In addition, these stakeholders were heavily engaged in both PRECINCT and non-PRECINCT events. The high level of concern for this stakeholder group is European, as the European Union (EU) lays out the framework for national entities to then implement in terms of Critical Infrastructure Protection (CIP), and the competent standardization bodies in Europe are the European Committee for Standardization (CEN) and the European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization (CENELEC). **Other Relevant Networks** were expected to be directly impacted by the project activities and results; nonetheless, as main targets of the liaison and cooperation activities, they were beneficial to PRECINCT in terms of expanding relationships with related

associations and stakeholders. Finally, **Citizens**, identified as stakeholders, they directly benefit from an increased protection of CI. However, the technical and restrictive nature of the project indicated that they could not be engaged in a meaningful way and were not the focus of the activities carried out over the course of the project.

Overall, PRECINCT touches a wide variety of stakeholders at different levels of governance. Below is a representation of the stakeholders PRECINCT targets classified by relevance and at which levels. Based on this classification, stakeholders were identified and then contacted by PRECINCT partners.

Figure 3-2: PRECINCT Stakeholders by level and relevance

3.1 Methodology for Selecting Stakeholders

The methodology for selecting stakeholders was quite simple, yet effective. Based on the categories described in the GA, EOS conducted desk research to identify stakeholders that would fit in the categories on the levels relevant to the PRECINCT project, as shown figure 3.2. Once the stakeholders were selected, they were enlisted in a file with contacts to be invited to the PRECINCT events. In addition, networks of PRECINCT partners, including stakeholders, were exploited for PRECINCT activities. For instance, EOS, shared the PRECINCT project invitations and information with its members highly interested in cyber-physical security. POLIS used its large network of municipalities to further disseminate the project results. UITP leveraged its network of public transport entities to discuss the PRECINCT project in the context of protecting public transport in the PRECINCT Conference and the UITP Global Public Transport Summit. Finally, stakeholders who signed letters of support and directly shared project results, such as the Emilia-Romagna region and the city and commune of Bologna, are also included in the list below.

3.2 Identification of Relevant Stakeholders¹

Section 3.2 will list the stakeholders that were identified by PRECINCT partners via its stakeholder mapping exercise, as well as any other stakeholders identified afterwards by various partners.

3.2.1 First Responders

Table 3-1: List of First Responder Stakeholders

Name of Stakeholder	Country	Level
DG European Commission Humanitarian Aid & Civil Protection (ECHO)	Belgium	European/International
Police Federale/Federale Politie	Belgium	National
Les sapeurs-pompiers de Belgique	Belgium	National
Les secours médicaux, sanitaires et psychosociaux	Belgium	National
La Protection Civile	Belgium	National
Carabinieri	Italy	National
Polizia di Stato	Italy	National
Corpo Nazionale dei Vigili del Fuoco	Italy	National
Protezione Civile	Italy	National
Police nationale	France	National
Gendarmerie nationale	France	National
Brigade des sapeurs-pompiers de Paris	France	Local
Bataillon de marins-pompiers de Marseille	France	Local
Fédération nationale de protection civile	France	National
Policía Nacional	Spain	National
Bomberos de Barcelona	Spain	Local
Cuerpo de bomberos de la Comunidad de Madrid	Spain	Local
Bomberos de la Generalidad de Cataluña	Spain	Local
Cuerpo de Bomberos de Las Palmas de Gran Canaria	Spain	Local
Protección Civil	Spain	National
Bundespolizei	Germany	National
Bundeskriminalamt	Germany	National
Feuerwehr	Germany	National
Bundesamt für Bevölkerungsschutz und Katastrophenhilfe	Germany	National
Korps Nationale Politie	Netherlands	National
Koninklijke Marechaussee	Netherlands	National
Brandweer Nederland	Netherlands	National
Hellenic Police - Ελληνική Αστυνομία	Greece	National
Hellenic Fire Service - Πυροσβεστικό Σώμα	Greece	National
Policja	Poland	National
Państwowa Straż Pożarna	Poland	National
Guarda Nacional Republicana	Portugal	National

¹ Citizens were omitted from identification, as this is a cross-cutting and large group and any attempt at identification could pose privacy issues.

Name of Stakeholder	Country	Level
Polícia de Segurança Pública	Portugal	National
Bombeiros de Portugal	Portugal	National
Autoridade Nacional de Emergência e Proteção Cívil	Portugal	National
Poliția Română	Romania	National
Jandarmeria Română	Romania	National
Inspectoratul General pentru Situații de Urgență - IGSU	Romania	National
Rendőrség	Hungary	National
Tűzoltóság	Hungary	National
Polgári védelem	Hungary	National
Bundespolizei	Austria	National
Landesfeuerwehrverband Oberösterreich	Austria	Local
Landesfeuerwehrverband Salzburg	Austria	Local
Landesfeuerwehrverband Tirol	Austria	Local
Politsei- ja Piirivalveamet	Estonia	National
GIGN	France	National
Emergency Response Coordination Centre	EU	European/International
Slovenian Police	Slovenia	National
Fire Brigade Ljubljana	Slovenia	Local
Municipality Police Ljubljana	Slovenia	Local

3.2.2 Critical Infrastructure Operators

Table 3-2: List of Critical Infrastructure Operators Stakeholders

Name of Stakeholder	Country	Level
Group ADP	France	National
Avinor	Norway	National
STIB/MVIB	Belgium	Local
DeLijn	Belgium	Local
RATP	France	Local
Transports Metropolitans de Barcelona	Spain	Local
Empresa Municipal de Transportes de Madrid	Spain	Local
Deutsche Bahn	Germany	National
SNCB	Belgium	National
SNCF	France	National
Irish Water	Ireland	National
ACCIONA	Spain	National
FN Motol	Czechia	National
The Fondazione Policlinico Universitario Agostino Gemelli	Italy	National
Hôpitaux universitaires de Genève - HUG	Switzerland	National
Universitätsklinikum Freiburg	Germany	National

Name of Stakeholder	Country	Level
University Medical Center Ljubljana	Slovenia	National
UZ Leuven Gasthuisberg Campus	Belgium	National
Heidelberg University Hospital	Germany	National
Oslo University Hospital	Norway	National
Clinic Klagenfurt am Woerthersee	Austria	National
Universitätsklinikum Essen	Germany	National
Hospital General Universitario Gregorio Marañón	Spain	National
L'HÔPITAL UNIVERSITAIRE PITIÉ SALPÊTRIÈRE	France	National
Academisch Medisch Centrum	Netherlands	National
General Hospital Ioanninon Chatzikosta	Greece	National
ING	Netherlands	International
AXA	France	International
Allianz	Germany	International
BNP Paribas	France	International
Santander	Spain	International
Assicurazioni Generali	Italy	International
HSBC	United Kingdom	International
Crédit Agricole Group	France	International
Munich RE	Germany	International
Zurich Insurance Group	Switzerland	International
Dexia	Belgium	National
Nordea	Finland	International
KBC Group	Belgium	International
Deutsche Bank	Germany	International
Barclays	United Kingdom	International
Osterreichs Energie	Austria	National
Febeg	Belgium	National
Electric Authority of Cyprus	Cyprus	National
Czech Association of Energy Sector Employers	Czechia	National
Green Power Denmark	Denmark	National
Eesti Elektritoostuse Liit	Estonia	National
Finnish Energy	Finland	National
Union Francaise de l'electricite	France	National
BDEW	Germany	National
Public Power Corporation of Greece	Greece	National
Samorka	Iceland	National
Electricity Association of Ireland	Ireland	National
Elettricità Futura	Italy	National
LEEA	Latvia	National
Nacionaline Lietuvos Energetikos Asociacija	Lithuania	National
LuxEnergie	Luxembourg	National
LeoEnergie	Luxembourg	National

Name of Stakeholder	Country	Level
Enemalta	Malta	National
Energie Nederland	Netherlands	National
Netbeheer Nederland	Netherlands	National
Energi Norge	Norway	National
Polish Electricity Association	Poland	National
Elecpor	Portugal	National
Institutul Național Român pentru Studiul Amenajării și Folosirii Surselor de Energie	Romania	National
Zväz zamestnávateľov energetiky Slovenska	Slovakia	National
EZS	Slovenia	National
Aelec	Spain	National
Energiföretagen	Sweden	National
AES	Switzerland	National
Türkiye Elektrik Sanayi Birliği	Turkey	National
Energy Networks Association	United Kingdom/Ireland	International
EnergyUK	United Kingdom	National
Association Francaise du Gaz	France	National
Federația Asociațiilor Companiilor de Utilități din Energie	Romania	National
CEPSA	Spain	National
Cheniere	United Kingdom	National
Deutsche Telekom	Germany	International
Vodafone Group	United Kingdom	International
Orange SA	France	International
Telefonica SA	Spain	International
Bouygues	France	International
Centre de Crise National	Belgium	National
Agence nationale de la sécurité des systèmes d'information	France	National
Secretariat General de la Defense et de le Securite Nationale	France	National
ELES	Slovenian	National

3.2.3 Policy & Decision-Makers

Table 3-3: List of Policy & Decision-Makers Stakeholders

Name of Stakeholder	Country	Level
SPF Mobilitéé et Transports	Belgium	National
Stockholm International Water Institute (SIWI)	Sweden	National
Siseministerium	Estonia	National
Ministère de l'Intérieur et des Outre-mer	France	National
The Ministry of Transport and Communications of Finland	Finland	National
Ministero del Interno	Italy	National
DG Justice & Home Affairs (HOME)	Belgium	European/International

Name of Stakeholder	Country	Level
DG Mobility & Transport (MOVE)	Belgium	European/International
DG European Commission Humanitarian Aid & Civil Protection (ECHO)	Belgium	European/International
Ministry for Infrastructure	Slovenia	National
Ministry for Citizen Protection	Greece	National
Agenzia per la Cybersicurezza Nazionale	Italy	National
SPF Interieur	Belgium	National
Emilia-Romagna Region	Italy	Local
Bologna Municipality (Comune di Bologna)	Italy	Local
Metropolitan City of Bologna	Italy	Local
SRM – Reti e Mobilità S.r.l.	Italy	Local
Antwerp city authorities	Belgium	Local
Swedish Civil Contingencies Agency	Sweden	National
ENISA	EU	European/International
Agenzia per la Cybersicurezza Nazionale	Italy	National
Ministry for Energy	Slovenia	National

3.2.4 Academia & Research

Table 3-4: List of Academia & Research Stakeholders

Name of Stakeholder	Country	Level
Federal Highway Research Institute	Germany	National
IHE-HELP Centre at the University of Dundee	Scotland	National
SINTEF	Norway	National
IWW Water Centre	Germany	National
WiCE	Germany	National
EIP (European Innovation Partnership) Water	Belgium	International
Allied Waters	Netherlands	International
Water and Energy Intelligence	Netherlands	National
WETSUS	Netherlands	National
Universita Cattolica del Sacre Cuore	Italy	National
Energy Management Institute	Bulgaria	National
FREE ICT EUROPE (FIE)	Netherlands	International
The European Gas Research Group	Belgium	International
EU-HYBNET	N/A	International
PRAETORIAN	N/A	International
7SHIELD	N/A	International
STRATEGY	N/A	International
Institute Jozef Stefan	Slovenia	National
The Forum of European Road Safety Research Institutes (FERSI)	N/A	International
Securegas	N/A	International
INFRARISK (ended 2016)	N/A	International
IMPROVER (ended 2018)	N/A	International
SAURON (ended 2020)	N/A	International
DEFENDER (ended 2020)	N/A	International
SmartResilience (2019)	N/A	International

Name of Stakeholder	Country	Level
CyberSANE	N/A	International
CyberSEAS	N/A	International
FINSEC (ended 2021)	N/A	International
ATENA (ended 2019)	N/A	International
Snowball (ended 2017)	N/A	International
LISA institute	N/A	International
GEA College	Slovenia	National
Faculty for Security Studies	Slovenia	National
Faculty for Governmental and European Studies	Slovenia	National

3.2.5 Industry & Technology Providers

Table 3-5: List of Industry & Technology Providers Stakeholders

Name of Stakeholder	Country	Level
ACI Europe	Belgium	European/International
Aquarius IT LTD.	United Kingdom	National
Aigües de Barcelona	Spain	National
De Watergroep	Belgium	National
Hessenwasser	Germany	National
Xylem Vue	US/EU	International
SUEZ en France	France	National
ACQUAINT	Netherlands	National
Czech Gas Association	Czechia	National
DCBrain	France	National
INOV	Portugal	National
Internet Society (ISOC)	Switzerland	International
ORGALIM	Belgium	International
Eurelectric	Belgium	International
Eurogas	Belgium	International
ENTSO-E	Belgium	International
SNEP	Slovenia	National
AQUA Consultancy	Netherlands	International
BUSINESSEUROPE	Belgium	International
DIGITALEUROPE	Belgium	International
EUROSMART	Belgium	International
OpenForum Europe AISBL	Belgium	International
Water Europe	Belgium	International
ISKRA	Slovenia	National
INFORMATIKA	Slovenia	National

3.2.6 Standardisation Bodies

Table 3-6: List of Standardisation Bodies Stakeholders

Name of Stakeholder	Country	Level
CEN	Belgium	European/ International
CENELEC	Belgium	European/ International

Name of Stakeholder	Country	Level
The Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers	Belgium	European/International
International Electrotechnical Commission	Switzerland	National
Slovenian Institute for Standardization	Slovenia	National

3.2.7 Other Relevant Networks

Table 3-7: List of Other Relevant Network Stakeholders

Name of Stakeholder	Country	Level
ECSCI	N/A	European/ International
UIC	France	European/International
International Association of CIP Professionals	N/A	European/International
Slovenian Association for Corporate Security	Slovenia	National
European Hospital and Healthcare Federation	Belgium	European/ International

3.3 Assessment of the PRECINCT Stakeholders

PRECINCT affects a wide variety of stakeholders, as one of its main objectives is to increase critical infrastructure resilience across Europe via its tools, assets, and approach. By assessing stakeholders at various levels involved in Critical Infrastructure Protection (CIP) and/or affected by cyber-physical threats and their cascading effects, PRECINCT has managed to identify a great number of stakeholders. This allowed PRECINCT to exploit a diverse network of technical knowledge for feedback and communicate its results. In addition, it helped to improve the potential uptake of the PRECINCT tools, as a wide variety of stakeholders were identified to participate in the development process of the tools and provided suggestions to increase their usability, according to stakeholders' needs.

As outlined in the early stages of the project, the PRECINCT Stakeholder Landscape comprises First Responders and Critical Infrastructure Operators. As the primary beneficiaries of the project and potential end-users, these stakeholders were prioritized as targets of the PRECINCT events among other stakeholders. Additionally, the Other Relevant Networks were useful in identifying more relevant stakeholders, as previously established networks, such as the European Cluster for Securing Critical Infrastructures (ECSCI) cluster, brought with them stakeholders for PRECINCT to exploit.

3.4 Engagement Strategy of Stakeholders

Once the stakeholders identified, the next step was to engage them to take part in the PRECINCT project. The main forum for engaging these stakeholders was the events organized by PRECINCT, in which the main outputs of the project were presented which gave them the opportunity to provide feedback to the PRECINCT partners.

Before each event, stakeholders were either contacted directly via their email or indirectly through social media, such as Twitter and LinkedIn and invited to take part in these events. Promotional materials, such as save the dates, invitations, and agendas were sent out to encourage stakeholders to join the events either online or in-person. Additionally, reminders were sent periodically to external stakeholders regarding the event, and EOS encouraged and reminded PRECINCT partners to further share the event materials with their networks and relevant stakeholders.

4 PRECINCT-organized Events

In the scope of T6.1 “PRECINCT Cyber-Physical Security Stakeholder Needs Knowledge Base”, the PRECINCT consortium organised 4 events: 2 stakeholder engagement workshops, a Conference, and a final commercial event. These events acted as the primary contact points between the PRECINCT project and its stakeholders and allowed stakeholders not only to be updated on the progress of the project, but also to provide feedback to the consortium regarding specific topics, namely the tools developed and the business exploitation, policy recommendation & standardisation, and training aspects.

4.1 1st Stakeholder Engagement Workshop

The 1st Stakeholder Engagement Workshop (SEW) was organized in Brussels on May 5th, 2022, and acted as the first PRECINCT organised event open to external participants. As the project had only started in September 2021, the first event was mainly focused on raising awareness of the project and its objectives, as well as presenting some initial findings and work. Additionally, this event was the first engagement that PRECINCT had with stakeholders. In total, the event was able to bring together 75 participants (out of 103 registered). During the event, despite the exception of a presentation conducted by the EU-HYBNET project, PRECINCT partners presented the work undertaken in each work package (WP), the WP overall objective, and the project’s vision. A full recording of the workshop was uploaded to YouTube on May 25th, 2022, for stakeholders access, and the full deck of the presentations were uploaded to the Zenodo community.

Figure 4-1: Stakeholders registered to the 1st SEW²

² The terms used for this registration form did not include PRECINCT Partners as an option, to differentiate external stakeholders. This graph includes PRECINCT partners.

Figure 4-2: Image from the 1st Stakeholder Engagement Workshop

4.1.1 Takeaways Learned

The purpose of the workshop was to present the main outputs of the project and ensure a strong interaction with industry CI stakeholders, end-users, citizens, and many other relevant stakeholders. The workshop included presentations from project partners on the work that had been accomplished so far and roundtable discussions to engage stakeholders on technical and business aspects for PRECINCT. The following provides an overview of the presentations and panel discussions which have been paraphrased.

Introduction

The workshop opened with a welcome and introduction from Mrs. Jenny Rainbird the PRECINCT project manager and representative of Inlecom, the project coordinators.

Mrs Rainbird introduced PRECINCT as a two-year international collaborative research project which started in October 2021, and brings together 40 technical experts and domain experts looking at understanding the challenges of protecting critical infrastructure in Europe. Mrs. Rainbird explained that the vision of the PRECINCT project is to bring together critical infrastructure stakeholders in a geographical area and have a common Cyber and physical security management approach to protecting critical infrastructure in that area considering the interconnectivity of critical infrastructure and the cascading effects that an attack can have on other infrastructure in that area. Mrs. Rainbird introduced the programme for the workshop, the full agenda can be found in Annex 8.1.

The first speaker was Mr. Gabriel Gunter a senior researcher and head of the smart transportation and infrastructures at the industry and security technologies research and innovation lab within Engineering research and development department.

Main Key Results and Roadmap

Dr. Gunter presented the PRECINCT reference framework specification which aims to improve security of Critical Infrastructures and deliver effective resilience management.

The first step in the development of the framework reference was to identify the main cyber physical and natural threats affecting critical infrastructure with particular reference to the infrastructures located in the PRECINCT four living labs. The main threats were identified and analysed by ICS taking into consideration the potential cascading effects and the relevant scenarios of the project Living Labs.

The second major activity looked at the interdependencies of critical infrastructure and the evaluation of the cascading effects. A dependency graph and cascading effect simulations was implemented in the Ljubiana and Antwerp Living Labs, where workshops were conducted. At the time of this workshop the work was in progress. The slides show an example of the dependency model for Ljubljana highlighting the identified nodes that have a crucial role in the critical infrastructure such as transportation, telecommunication and the energy nodes and for Antwerp those related to potential flooding.

The resilience methodological framework is being developed by RDS consisting of several steps, starting from the identification and the quantification of the services used then to develop resilience indicators.

The final step in the framework reference is the quantification of the vulnerabilities of CIs. The PRECINCT project will look at identifying the main taxonomies in terms of risk in order to have a common understanding about risk and potential threat. PRECINCT will also provide business and technical the requirements specifications and identification of relevant Standards.

Questions from participants can be summarised as follows:

Q1) can you explain what are the benefits of the frameworks you introduced for potential users beyond the project?

A1) One of the main benefits of this reference framework is to identify a baseline which could be used by the different PRECINCT partners in order for all stakeholders to be “talking the same language” we have started analyzing the main threats scenarios for each individual LL to identify the threats and interdependencies which will be used as a baseline

BluePrints and Knowledge Graphs

Mrs. Rainbird introduced the speakers. Dr. Djibrilla Amadou-Kountche (AKKA) received his PhD in Machine Learning in 2013. He joined AKKA in June 2018 as a project manager and his expertise are machine learning, security, privacy, cooperative intelligence and transportation systems and wireless networks

Dr. Stathis Zavvos (VLTN) received his PhD in computer science in 2019 and is well versed in several artificial intelligence areas including machine learning intelligent agents game theory and genetic algorithms he's currently the head of artificial intelligence at VLTN.

The main goal is to reuse package tools or knowledge from previous research in the protection of CI and deliver this in a PRECINCT blueprint repository so that this can be deployed, tested and experimented on for example in the LLs. For example we can make a Digital Twin or a knowledge graph available in the form of a blueprint with a description, this can be deployed and then feedback can be provided in the form of configuration files. To avoid the issues related to different languages PRECINCT is proposing to use Tosca which is a standard to facilitate the deployment and orchestration of an application independently from the provider.

The speakers used the disaster in the Fukushima nuclear plant as an example of unexpected cascading effects of a natural disaster demonstrating that PRECINCT can help develop strategies to counter and recover from disasters like this one.

Serious Games

Mrs. Rainbird introduced Dr. Daniel McCrum, Assistant Professor in structural engineering at the school of civil engineering, University college Dublin.

In PRECINCT we have the ambition to create a Serious Game to help critical infrastructure owner operators and users understand their resilience and also use this as a training tool. The Interdependency Graph identifies CIs with nodes and the links between them which can be used to assess the vulnerability and the resilience of these nodes and their cascading effects. The ambition is to use Machine Learning techniques and data mining will be used to help understand the gameplay and generate Game play records.

The Antwerp LL flooding was used as an example in the presentation to show the steps of Game play. The game has character selection including a director, a defender and an attacker. The director is responsible for deciding the scenario. The defender implements the mitigation strategy depending on the available resources. The attacker attacks the assets which impacts the resilience of these nodes. In the example the Kennedy tunnel was attacked and the mitigation strategy was put in place. The interface displays useful information to the user. This will be further developed in collaboration with the LL partners.

Questions from participants can be summarised as follows:

Q1) you gave the example of sand sandbags and re building a bridge, in the game scenario as a response. I was wondering whether the time aspect was important for calculating resilience because (in this example) the tools can be short or longer term.

A1) ultimately I think these are going to be discrete calculations to include the time dependency nature.

Q2) I am interested in how to connect the Director and attacker and defender. Do you plan to have “matchmaking” or is it more stored and there's some kind of level selection and around play?

A2) This is something we will investigate with the LLs when we meet with them this month. Where we'll find out exactly who they want to be those people for example the game director doesn't get directly involved in the game but they set up the game and scenario. We will find out what they LL partners want those people to achieve and how they will learn.

PRECINCT Architecture and Implementation

Mrs Rainbird introduced the speaker Dr, David Vermeer who has been working at IMEC for the past eight years and currently serving as an operations lead at the sustainable and urban environment center.

Dr. Vermeer outlined three main blocks within PRECINCT with the first part, ending in July, focusing on user story maps for digital twins and the architecture for living labs. The second part shifts towards development, creating a library of digital twin components, integrating with technical elements of other work packages, and emphasizing interactions with tools like serious games and AI platforms. The final block, extending into the project's last year, involves the instantiation and customization of digital twins for living labs. The speaker also discusses the scoping exercise, the logical architecture design, and the precinct capabilities framework that guides the technology-agnostic approach.

In terms of development, the project adopts an iterative process, beginning with deploying a core digital twin reference prototype, integrating various components like AI tools and serious games, and creating a diverse library of digital twin components to cater to different contexts and use cases. The importance of interoperability and adherence to international and European data standards are highlighted. The architecture will be applied to

living labs through a reference architecture and the use of the precinct ecosystem platform, ensuring specific instantiations for each living lab based on their unique use cases, integrations, and AI models. The anticipated deliverables include reports on user story maps, architectural blueprints, design guidelines, integration tools, and the final software application for digital twins, expected at different stages of the project.

Questions from participants can be summarised as follows:

Q1) How does the DT model compare to the Knowledge Graph that you mentioned?

A1) a knowledge graph is essentially an interconnected instance of one or multiple twins. They highlight the significance of the open digital twin framework in providing capabilities to easily map out these twins, including their associated artifacts (underlying data) and functions (models). The emphasis is on maintaining continuous management and governance of the knowledge graph, particularly in complex scenarios like precincts with multiple stakeholders, use cases, and twin environments. The ability to describe potential changes in a digital twin is crucial for effective governance in such dynamic settings.

PRECINCT Living Labs

Mrs Rainbird introduced Mrs. Shirley Delanoy a researcher from the VIAS institute an independent and multi-disciplinary Belgian knowledge center specialized in road safety mobility and security. VIAS will lead the Living Lab operation, coordinate the overall planning and develop and implement a monitoring learning system and validation approach.

Mrs Delanoy gave a brief introduction to the PRECINCT Living Labs.

- 1) In ljubljana the scenario will focus on the threats on a physical threat the bomb and on cyber attack with and simultaneous attack to critical parts of the critical infrastructure and on the electricity and communication operators which provide an important service for business continuity in the transport mobility.
- 2) In Antwerp the scenario is a natural disaster of flooding with cascading effects on water and traffic and involving the energy operator
- 3) In Athens the focus will be on cyber and physical threats as a such as a cyber attack to the airport and an earthquake
- 4) Bologna the focus is cyber physical attacks on rail and or airport infrastructure combined with fake news and a cyber attack on comms/

The Transferability demonstrators are Luxembourg with a focus on energy telecommunication, Ireland with a focus on transport and energy and Uruguay with a focus on water electricity and technical telecom critical infrastructure.

Mr. John Limaxis introduced the Athens Living Lab, focusing on enhancing resilience against cyber-physical incidents impacting urban transport in Athens. The lab comprises three critical infrastructures: Athens International Airport, the main road operator to the airport, and Athens Metro. The objective is to test platforms and tools, emphasizing the digital twin threat scenario and utilizing mock-ups. The living lab aims to increase transportation resilience, with key performance indicators (KPIs) centered on reducing disruption downtime, improving road system capability, and enhancing response procedures.

The lab has formulated seven threat scenarios, covering airport, metro, and road infrastructures, addressing terrorist attacks, cyber intrusions, earthquakes, and other incidents. The digital twin scenario, a simulation combining cyber intrusion and terrorist actions, aims to test tools under realistic threat conditions. Mock-ups for the digital twin involve an operational mode for viewing events and a simulation mode for creating or evaluating scenarios. The digital twin relies on relevant data sets such as statics for airport facilities, road sensors, passenger flow, and flight information. The future plan involves continued collaboration, technical validation at month 12, and obtaining baseline measurements for KPIs.

The Antwerp Living Lab, introduced by Mrs. Delannoy, addresses the growing threat of flooding and the severe consequences of global warming, particularly in the Antwerp region. The lab focuses on flash floods caused by heavy rainfall and employs a methodology to implement, monitor, and evaluate technologies aimed at interconnecting critical infrastructure systems (CIS) to enhance decision-making by the police and fire department during disaster events. The lab's user story centers on responding to flash flooding in the city of Antwerp, emphasizing the cascading effects on traffic infrastructure, energy blackouts, and impacts on essential services.

The scope of the Antwerp LL involves utilizing a precinct reference framework to establish dependency maps, deploying technologies like the series game and digital twin, and implementing a three-step process of design, operation, and validation to enhance resilience and response capabilities. Major stakeholders include PS coordinating the lab, Antwerp police managing the CIS coordination center, ENG designing the digital twin, KU Leuven contributing to flooding models, and WaterLink providing data support. The lab aims to enhance understanding of resilience, improve risk analysis tools, and create an early warning system for citizens' benefit. The use of the design sprint methodology in developing the digital twin involves user workshops, data analysis, storyboarding, and mock-ups to enhance the end-user experience. The lab is progressing with the goal of interconnecting flooding and traffic CIS to support decision-making during emergencies in Antwerp.

Dr. Denis Čaleta presented the Lubiana Living Lab focusing on the collaboration among four critical infrastructure providers: multi-modal transport (rail and bus), electricity, and telecommunications in Ljubljana. The Living Lab also involves the municipality police of Ljubljana, recognizing the interconnectedness of these infrastructures in the city. To comprehend the entire operational environment, technical partners and supporting partners are included, with an emphasis on developing tools for the project. The Living Lab aims to explore cascading and interdependencies among different critical infrastructures, focusing on two main scenarios: physical and cyber attacks.

The proximity of critical infrastructure providers in Ljubljana emphasizes the need to understand their interconnections and dependencies. The project addresses the upcoming development of a new mobility hub in Ljubljana, highlighting the importance of coordinating multiple centers within each critical infrastructure and establishing connections with national authorities. The proposal includes demanding Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to assess not only new technologies but also procedures, responses, and interdependencies among critical infrastructures. The digital twin scenario chart illustrates the complexity of the situation, aiming to enhance situational awareness through a common 3D operational coordination center.

Dr. Giuseppe Brancaccio presented the Living lab of Bologna which includes partners from Lepida service provider for the region Emilio Romagna, Bologna airport, FS technology the railway company, The region Emilio Romani, the Marconi Express, the port authority of Ravenna and ITL the coordinator of the living lab.

Dr. Brancaccio presented a map of the region and infrastructure road and transport network. The scenarios which will be investigated include a natural extreme weather event and a cyber attack.

Partners' feedback on the business requirements

Mrs Rainbird introduced Dr Mark Bennett, senior innovation and commercialization consultant at intercom commercial pathways.

Dr. Bennett outlined the stakeholder map and user segments in a project focused on critical infrastructure protection (CIP). The supply side, primarily the private sector, involves technology suppliers, integrators, strategy consultants, and security operation centers engaged in CIP activities. On the user side, three levels are identified: Level 1 managing their own critical infrastructure, Level 2 coordinating regionally, and Level 3 coordinating nationally or internationally. The user segments are categorized into CI operators, emergency services managers, and regional/national response coordinators. The goal is to develop a valid proposition for these segments using

the value proposition canvas approach, understanding their needs and aligning solutions. Dr. Bennett also discussed the technology supplier side, emphasizing the importance of addressing user groups' pains and gains, using the example of CI owners/operators who seek gains in visualization, modeling, training, and efficient strategies while facing pains like financial losses, coordination challenges, and environmental damage. The approach aims to create customer-centric solutions in work package six of the project.

Comments from participants can be summarised as follows:

C1) “ you don't always know what you don't know “one of the things ITL is hoping to gain from PRECINCT is a better understanding of potential issues, those “unknowns”.

C2) Thinking about the legislative aspect, there is a new directive proposal at the EC which will give some new tasks for CI operators and entities so perhaps it would be good to highlight here. Meeting regulations as they develop.

Dr. Bennett discussed the customer profiles for emergency services managers, regional coordinators, and technology suppliers. The emergency services managers prioritize coordinating activities, maintaining regional assets' efficiency, and enhancing response effectiveness. They aim to reduce threats' impact and protect public safety. Common gains involve visualization modeling, effective training, and rapid response. Challenges include environmental damage, loss of life, and organizational coordination issues. Feedback suggests incorporating financial considerations for public sector users. Regional coordinators focus on coordinating multiple assets, improving coordination, protecting property, staff, and the public, and reducing threat impacts and mitigation costs.

Dr. Bennett outlined key business requirements, emphasizing the need for predictive tools, visualizing vulnerabilities, user-friendly solutions, and rapid restoration of operations. Participants suggest considering real-time event response, prioritizing understanding before action, and standardizing insights for users. They also highlight the challenge of integrating private industry players and addressing budgetary constraints in implementing critical infrastructure protection solutions. The discussion underscores the need for market development in coordinated tools for national-level emergency response.

Comments from participants can be summarised as follows:

C3) (IMEC) I see the need for standardized insights in smart cities, addressing challenges in the continuously changing landscape and evolving disasters. They highlight the difficulty in integrating solutions from the private industry cohesively and express the importance of consistent strategies. The discussion also touches on interoperability issues among suppliers and users, with a focus on matching solutions to user requirements. I acknowledge budget constraints for local governments in implementing comprehensive solutions and suggests exploring this further in upcoming workshops.

Morning Conclusions

Mrs. Rainbird expressed gratitude to the morning's speakers and audience for their engagement. The session covered the challenges being addressed, the precinct's vision, collaborative efforts, and technologies like knowledge graphs and digital twins. Insights from living labs highlighted operational plans, identified threats, and outlined desired impacts. The discussion also delved into business requirements. After a lunch break, the agenda includes roundtable discussions and a presentation from the EU Hibernate project in the afternoon.

PRECINCT's Future Technical Aspects – Panel Discussion

Moderator: Mark Miller (CPT), Speakers: Daniel McCrum (UCD), Stefan , Lefever (IMEC), Stefan Schauer (AIT), Gabriele Giunta (ENG), Lorcan Connolly (RDS)

Q1 to LC, Risk assessment has been universally accepted as a tool for decades to analyze impacts of natural and man-made threats to critical infrastructure what are the benefits of the precinct resilience methodological framework over the traditional advanced risk assessment approaches?

A1) LC - LL emphasised the importance of the precinct framework in addressing risk from a service provision perspective. It allows for quantifying the impact of hazards in monetary terms across different critical infrastructures, considering interoperability and coordination. Resilience is highlighted as a key factor, enabling the examination of temporal aspects and incorporation of organizational considerations beyond physical infrastructure.

Q2) How are digital twins used to simulate the vulnerabilities and to address the issues that have come out of this new approach toward looking at risk assessment?

A2) – SS- Interoperability is crucial in achieving critical infrastructure resilience, with a focus on digital technology managing data and computation. Business requirement one, proposed by Mark, emphasizes the need for digital twins in precincts to facilitate decision-making. The challenge lies in ensuring interoperability for uniform data utilization in modelling the impacts of changes to critical infrastructure. The TOSCA framework is suggested for abstraction, but the complexity requires additional solutions like asset registries and scenario managers. Resilient digital twins should evolve from a strategic to an operational tool, enabling bidirectional interaction between physical and virtual assets. This is particularly important in complex scenarios, such as AI applications in precincts, where transparency and human intelligence integration are vital for decision control. The value of digital twins lies in making technology assets accountable not only to strategic decision-makers but also in enhancing resilience in human and machine interactions.

Q2 to GG - What are the main technological challenges in CI security and protection that we're going to address in PRECINCT?

A2) GG - The critical infrastructure we're working on is a complex cyber-physical system, and the boundaries between physical and cyber security are blurred. There's a need for integrated security solutions, like security intelligence and cyber intelligence, to address cyber and physical threats. The European Commission has emphasized a joint approach to consider both domains. Our focus is on providing innovative solutions for the integration of cyber and physical systems, utilizing resilience indicators and data-driven approaches, including big data analytics and artificial intelligence. The digital twin is crucial for simulating real-time data from infrastructure, enabling effective simulations and testing of solutions. Presently, we concentrate on interdependencies and cascading effects within a virtual network of interconnected critical infrastructures. We aim to provide concrete solutions for their integration, moving beyond individual infrastructure security. Additionally, serious games are part of our approach to enhance understanding and responses in interconnected critical infrastructure scenarios.

Q3 to SS- the integration of the interdependencies graph and cascading effects simulation is a crucial aspect of our precinct project. It involves understanding and illustrating how critical infrastructures depend on and relate to each other. The interdependency graph compiles information from experts and operators, creating an abstracted overview of how individual systems respond to specific incidents. This graph, along with the knowledge graph mentioned earlier, forms the basis for cascading effects simulation, revealing how changes in one system affect others. This information is then integrated into the digital twin, providing a comprehensive view of cascading effects across infrastructures. The serious game aspect utilizes this data to train end users on

handling such scenarios effectively. The overarching goal is to address uncertainties in incidents like floods, providing a holistic understanding of their impacts across different critical infrastructures.

C1) MM The serious game, building on Stefan's points, serves as both a vulnerability assessment tool and a means to visualize and understand complex scenarios. It integrates resilience scores and incorporates input from others, making it a valuable training tool. The game allows for repeated play, learning from mistakes without real-world consequences, and envisions multiple scenarios for ongoing training.

C2) MM - You discussed the expanding attack surface for cyber threats due to advancements like automated systems in water pumping or captainless ships. You're interested in managing these changes in the knowledge graph effectively. From the perspective of critical infrastructure interdependency, the focus is on understanding the effects of threats rather than individual sources. By abstracting away from specifics and emphasizing factors like operational status and risk changes, the goal is to create a more manageable and stable knowledge graph, reducing the frequency of updates while still addressing potential threats.

Q4) MM - Does the quantification of resilience have an impact on the knowledge graph?

A1) SS- In dealing with the ever-expanding landscape of cyber and physical threats, my perspective is that a key solution lies in emphasizing preparedness. This involves conducting effective risk assessments to identify vulnerabilities in complex critical infrastructures. By evaluating resilience quantitatively and qualitatively, we gain insights into how well we can mitigate and protect against various threats. The Resilience Framework, as discussed in my presentation, aids in analyzing resilience indicators across technological, societal, economic, and organizational aspects. This ongoing process allows us to gauge our infrastructure's readiness against evolving threats, considering changing risk assessment approaches. This comprehensive approach, addressing both vulnerabilities and resilience, offers a dynamic strategy to confront emerging challenges.

Q5 – Will the serious games concept adapt to threat surface changes?

A1) In PRECINCT, we're focusing on specific threat sources for each living lab, considering a standardized approach for threat sources between the digital twin and serious game. There's flexibility in the serious game, and as we meet living lab partners, we'll adapt based on their insights. Regarding future technologies, digital twins are in the spotlight, but projects like PRECINCT contribute to proving their real value. The integration of tools in PRECINCT, considering multi-modal infrastructure and various hazards, is innovative and aligns with the Commission's focus on regional authorities. The ultimate goal is an international approach with precincts using the same methodology. Existing solutions from previous research projects are crucial for demonstrating innovation, and the tight 24-month timeline adds urgency to integrating proven solutions for practical use in the market.

Q6 could the DT become another CI and how you envision to protect it?

A1) The digital twin's vulnerability is a crucial consideration. A national digital twin infrastructure, like any IT system, faces potential cyber threats. Protecting it requires expertise beyond my scope, but your point on its potential as a critical infrastructure is valid. Incorporating this into risk analysis and knowledge graphs is essential, especially examining cascading effects on interconnected critical infrastructures. To safeguard digital twins, a distributed and federated approach, ensuring interoperability and expressiveness among cooperating twins, seems pivotal. Awareness of the system's vulnerability is crucial, acknowledging it as a potential playground for attackers. Technical measures exist, but also consider threats like adversarial examples affecting the accuracy of the digital twin. This aligns with discussions on hybrid warfare and attacks, as addressed in upcoming presentations.

Q7) From the LL perspective how are all the tools that have been mentioned going to be incorporated in the DT?

A1) In summary, the interdependency graph is collaboratively built in the living lab through workshops, both online and offline. This graph, derived from operator knowledge, offers a comprehensive view of interdependencies. The resulting insights can be shared with critical infrastructure operators, aiding them in understanding dependencies within the living lab. This information is integrated into other technologies like digital twin and serious games. The deployment of tools is a nuanced process involving instantiation, tailoring solutions to each living lab's unique needs. Looking forward, the precinct tools can be delivered as standalone offerings or as an integrated package, providing both consultancy services and a comprehensive precinct system. Ultimately, the goal is to offer a versatile solution that enhances resilience.

Q8) How can we effectively integrate cyber security, safety, and resilience into critical infrastructures like power plants, emphasizing the importance of a dynamic model to manage risks in industries and factories?

A1) - It's crucial to consider the value of real-time resilience and risk estimation in addition to pre-emptive planning. However, the challenge lies in whether the limitation is due to computational power or the need for more intelligent algorithms. Achieving real-time assessment, especially post-PRECINCT, could significantly benefit critical infrastructure operators. While physical events like floods are well-defined and measurable, cyber events pose challenges due to the lack of sufficient data. The idea of live updating the simulation was discussed, but it was deemed a potential future direction beyond the current PRECINCT project.

C1) Agree with Daniel that real-time resilience is crucial for the future. Stefan mentioned barriers like computing power and data availability. While dynamic mode in the living lab involves users testing precinct tools, it won't involve real-time emergencies. Emphasized the importance of interdependencies in precinct's focus. Validation in the living lab includes trying various scenarios with real users and data without real-time events. Living lab wisdom involves continuous learning, suggesting standardization for comparing different simulations and storing artifacts for future analysis. Storing precinct actions is crucial for learning from the living lab experience.

Q9) I was very interested in the concept of monetary cost. How stable are AI-driven solutions in handling the uncertainties associated with valuing intangible aspects such as life loss or productivity, especially when stakeholders determine the value?

The panel discussed the importance of considering costs and stability in infrastructure decisions, emphasizing the need for objectivity and collaboration among various stakeholders. The quantification of factors like human life and delay costs requires consensus during the discussion period. The panel also touches upon the challenge of dealing with uncertainties, suggesting a probabilistic approach for modeling cascading effects in the face of unpredictable incidents. The conversation then shifted to the presentation of outcomes to decision-makers, highlighting the difficulty of conveying uncertainty and proposing more advanced methods, such as stochastic optimization, to aid in decision-making. The discussion ends with brief remarks from panelists expressing their key takeaways and hopes for the future of precincts, emphasizing user-centricity, integration of cutting-edge systems, and the comprehensive overview of managed infrastructures. The focus is on practical applications, the potential for synthetic data, and the need for commercialization and demonstration of integrated tools in living labs.

Critical Infrastructure Protection EU-HYBNET Project

Mrs Rainbird introduced the speaker Dr. Päivi Mattila Director of security of the research program at laureate university of applied scientists sciences in Finland

Dr. Mattila expressed pleasure in presenting the EU-Hybernet project, emphasizing its relevance to critical infrastructure protection. The agenda included an introduction to EU-Hybernet, insights from the project, recommendations for countering hybrid threats, and future aspects.

The EU-Hybernet project aims to build European capabilities to counter hybrid threats. The process involves mapping pan-European security practitioners' needs, vulnerabilities, and capabilities, followed by analyzing gaps and needs. Innovations, both technological and non-technological, are then mapped, and promising solutions are tested in training and exercise events. The project focuses on the European Commission's hybrid threats conceptual model, addressing 13 domains where threats take place. The four core themes of EU-Hybernet include future trends of hybrid threats, cyber and future technologies, resilient civilians and administration, and information and strategic communication.

The presentation highlighted threats identified in the project, such as the exploitation of critical infrastructure weaknesses, foreign direct investments, space interference, disruptive innovations, and foreign interference in information institutions. One promising innovation is the Common Information Sharing and Analysis Environment (CSI), facilitating collaborative investigations.

Insights for the future included the need for reporting weak signals in directives, public-private cooperation in critical infrastructure, a holistic approach, addressing hybrid attacks on space, managing indirect investments, ensuring European self-sufficiency, and identifying attackers' signatures through pan-European information sharing.

Dr. Mattila stressed the importance of non-technological innovations, particularly in training and serious gaming, to counter hybrid threats effectively.

Drivers and Barriers for implementation of new CIP Solutions – Panel Discussion

Moderator: Mark Bennett (ICP), Speakers: Marisa Escalante Martinez, (TCNL), Päivi Mattila (LAUREA), Vito Morreale (ENG), Benoit Baurens (AKKA), Denis Čaleta (ICS)

Q1) MB - What you see is the key problem rising from the combined cyber physical threats and or cascading effects?

A1) PM - It is important to address cascading effects in cyber-physical threats and attacks. There is a need for well-prepared systems that support information sharing, joint reactions, coordinated actions, and training. The complexity of the system, especially with cascading effects, is identified as a key challenge. Communication, knowledge sharing, and awareness are crucial, as operators tend to focus on their own business and may not fully understand the consequences that could cascade. The discussion emphasizes the benefits of projects like "Precinct" in raising awareness, providing tools like knowledge graphs, and formalizing the potential cascading effects on critical infrastructures, ultimately contributing to a more prepared and responsive global ecosystem.

A2) DC - The main issue in our operational environment is the persistence of working in security silos, dividing them into physical and cyber domains. Recently, we've recognized the addition of safety silos, but there's a lack of common understanding among these silos. Establishing a shared terminology is crucial to align perceptions of threats, such as cyber attacks. The complexity of technology exacerbates the problem, making it challenging to find experts who comprehend the entire system within critical infrastructure. In multi-organizational environments with diverse sectors, achieving a comprehensive operational picture becomes troublesome. Another key point is the need for awareness among strategic management. While operational and expert levels may understand security risks, the top management often prioritizes financial and operational threats, relegating security to a secondary concern. In the realm of critical infrastructure, the strong involvement of the private sector necessitates fostering private-public partnerships. Bridging the gap in understanding between private and state perspectives on critical infrastructure is essential, making such partnerships a top priority at every level—strategic, operational, and tactical.

A3) VM - The question addresses two main orthogonal dimensions of the problem: the integration of cyber and physical aspects and the interdependencies within and across organizations. This integration poses a challenge

not only technologically but also in terms of processes and responsibilities, given the separate management of cybersecurity and physical security. Managing the interdependent systems is complicated, and the lack of emphasis on achieving situational awareness exacerbates the problem. Situational awareness involves more than monitoring; it requires assessing and evaluating risks before events occur, especially in the face of complex, multi-threaded attack scenarios with weak signals. The complexity also extends to the preparation phase, where joint planning for responses and mitigation is crucial, highlighting the often-overlooked human factor in both contributing to and solving the challenges. This underscores the need to consider people's mindset, education, training, and knowledge when designing and deploying solutions, even in critical infrastructure where awareness might be lacking.

Q2) MB - What are the drivers which are forcing CI infrastructure operators to adopt new CIP solutions given the kind of problems we've talked about?

A1) PM- The critical entity's resilience directive proposal urges critical infrastructure operators to identify and disclose vulnerabilities, fostering cooperation in the face of cyber threats. While it poses challenges in managing vulnerabilities, it is a positive step for enhancing protection and future collaboration.

Q3) MB - What could be enablers to help us overcome barriers and get these kind of solutions on the market and what one thing would you want PRECINCT to focus on going forward?

A1) PM - Living labs bring together various actors from different fields, such as telecommunication operators, cities, transport entities (including train operators and airports). This collaborative approach is crucial for coordinating responses to large-scale disruptions and safeguarding critical infrastructure. By fostering discussions and trust among these diverse operators, vulnerabilities are shared, and the development of tools for future cooperation is facilitated. Do you believe precinct should also prioritize these efforts, as they seem to be doing already.

Q4) MB - What are the external drivers for adopters to take on CIP solutions?

A1) Sharing information promptly is crucial to address potential vulnerabilities in critical infrastructure. Quick reactions minimize consequences compared to delayed responses. Directives and political decisions can positively influence various stakeholders, urging them to establish rules, preparedness, and training. Standardization, including common information models and ontologies, fosters a shared language, facilitating collaboration among different operators. Integrating digital twins into serious games for training enhances innovative approaches to analyze human behavior in various scenarios. This emphasizes the importance of collaboration, common understanding, and uniformity in legal aspects, directives, and information models.

A2) VM - To maintain integration with existing solutions, providers should prioritize awareness tools for operators, addressing the gap in understanding the full risk. Research projects like PRECINCT need to focus on integrating the physical and cyber worlds, emphasizing information sharing with standardized models. Additionally, there's a need to enhance the critical infrastructure protection life cycle by emphasizing preparation, risk assessment, threat intelligence, and post-event analysis. Integration, awareness, and standardized information models emerge as key drivers and needs from both perspectives.

A3) DC - In a security-driven context, the main push factor for critical infrastructure providers is the constant threat of cyber attacks, exemplified by recent crises like the one in Ukraine. This necessitates enhanced preparedness through better technology. Additionally, modularity is crucial, as an open system allows integration with various solutions, overcoming vendor-specific limitations. Addressing challenges at different stages is vital, requiring a robust yet simple and versatile technology. Adaptability to evolving threats and maintenance over time is essential, emphasizing the need for standardization to ensure responsive technology evolution.

Q5) MB - Does anyone have any perspectives on whether the market is ready for what we are developing?

A1) MEM – It is not clear whether the public and the private sectors are ready to collaborate. So public private initiatives are very important. Maturity of the market may vary between countries/regions. Also it may not be possible to have very mature technologies because of the nature of evolving attacks. Developers have to be good salesmen and speak to management. Technologies don't address all problems and integration is important.

Q6) MB - On the issue of data sharing could a trusted third party would be an enabler or a facilitator for something like the precinct system?

A1 – The panel discussed the idea of creating a system or platform for precinct security, and there were several key points made. Firstly, there was a suggestion that instead of having a single integrated system, it might be more practical to have a framework or toolbox with various tools and solutions. This approach allows for flexibility in choosing tools based on specific needs.

The discussion also touched on the issue of whether critical infrastructure operators are willing to trust third parties to manage parts of their processes or security. The point was made that, in practice, they already do so when using cloud solutions. However, deploying security solutions poses a challenge, and trust becomes a significant factor. The panel acknowledged that this trust barrier needs to be overcome.

Additionally, the conversation delved into the sharing of information. There was a distinction between sharing raw data, which is already done with trusted suppliers, and sharing a higher level of data or intelligence. The panel emphasized that while sharing higher-level information is more challenging, it is essential for achieving integrated security among interdependent critical infrastructure operators.

Lastly, the discussion expanded to consider interdependencies not only between critical infrastructure entities but also involving providers. The example was given that if a provider is attacked, it affects both the provider and the critical infrastructure relying on their services. This interconnectedness highlights the importance of addressing security challenges collectively

Questions from the floor:

Q1 - When you have two CI operators which are also competitors how is data sharing managed?

A1 - depends on various factors such as location, operators, tools used, and political considerations. Decision-making can vary based on local expertise, technical maturity, and negotiation outcomes.

Q2 – Threats are becoming more common. How much is public funding from central governments a barrier to this type of innovation?

A1 - The public sector may play a role in standardization and initiating complex scenarios, while the private sector can take over for solutions.

C – JR – from my experience funding usually follows some incident or disaster.

Q3 - Are there any other either enablers to getting CIP solutions widely adopted or barriers to that that we haven't mentioned?

A1) I think that training it's a very important enabler

A2) The main problem we're facing, not only nationally but also with EU funds, is a lack of proactive crisis planning. We tend to react to crises rather than anticipating and preparing for them. My view is that top management needs to better understand and support costly yet crucial initiatives, enabling the swift implementation of advanced technology solutions for improved preparedness. Additionally, there's a significant issue with awareness at various levels—operators and critical infrastructure personnel often lack awareness of potential risks, especially concerning complex systems with interconnected vulnerabilities. This lack of awareness extends beyond internal issues to problems arising from the interdependence of organizations, which is a pressing concern in today's context.

The panel discussed the importance of awareness in critical infrastructure protection, emphasizing a shift from a reactive to a goal-oriented approach. They highlighted the need to consider the ultimate goals of protection and the acceptability of service degradation in different sectors. The discussion touched upon the correlation between cybersecurity and physical protection, as well as the challenges posed by the supply chain. Additionally, the integration of NIST directives and the merging of cybersecurity and physical protection processes were discussed. The panel emphasized the importance of staying customer-centric for widespread adoption.

Closing remarks

Mrs Rainbird thanked attendees, speakers and project partners and invited everyone to keep up to date with the project via the website and social media.

Organisational Aspects

After the 1st SEW, it became clear that PRECINCT should and could reach a larger audience. Additionally, since the first event's content was mainly focused on presenting the initial work and objectives of the project to stakeholders, a more interactive approach for the next event was decided to have stakeholders more engaged. To increase the audience, and expand the liaison and cooperation activities, PRECINCT partners reached out to its sister project PRAETORIAN in order to co-organise the 2nd Stakeholder engagement workshop. This co-organisation allowed the projects to invite their stakeholder groups and increase their awareness. The partners involved also ensured that the planning of the next workshop would focus on having more interactive formats such as panels, working groups, etc. to raise stakeholders' active involvement in these engagement workshops.

4.2 2nd Stakeholder Engagement Workshop

The 2nd SEW was held 6 months after the first, in Brussels on November 22nd, 2022, and was co-organised with the PRAETORIAN project: a sister project of PRECINCT. This 2nd SEW aimed at build upon the first and bringing together the stakeholders of both projects to present how each project is approaching the same problem and update stakeholders on the PRECINCT work done since the last event. The event agenda (see section 8.2) also included working group sessions for the participants to further develop topics vital to the work of both projects (standardisation & policy recommendations and PRECINCT & PRAETORIAN training and capacity building programmes) and a general session on exploitation. The participation in this SEW increased from the last from 75 to 109, signaling a positive trend that allowed PRECINCT to further reach stakeholders.

Stakeholders Registered for the 2nd Stakeholder Engagement Workshop

Figure 4-3: Stakeholders registered to the 2nd SEW

Figure 4-4: Image from the 2nd Stakeholder Engagement Workshop

4.2.1 Takeaways Learned

Mr. Giovanni Nizato from Inlecom opened the joint Workshop between the PRECINCT and the PRAETORIAN projects. We appreciate your presence as we embark on a full day of interactive presentations. The significance of today extends beyond regional boundaries, bringing together individuals who benefit from the interconnected and advanced infrastructures shaping our daily lives, from energy supply to transportation. As users and stakeholders, we share common experiences, and today's collaborative effort aims to strengthen the network of critical infrastructures.

Both projects have actively engaged stakeholders and users, fostering a shared understanding of their needs. The precinct project, for example, has progressed through phases, identifying user requirements and aligning solutions with business needs. On the other hand, the praetorian project has undertaken regular progress updates, workshops, and demonstrations to gather valuable feedback from stakeholders. Despite different approaches, these projects converge on the importance of early-stage feedback for technological development. Today's agenda includes project reviews, content presentations, interactive sessions, and workshops, emphasizing active participation and networking opportunities. We encourage you to make the most of this collaborative space, acknowledging the investment of time and effort from all involved parties.

PRECINCT: First Year Results & Highlight, Mrs Jenny Rainbird (Inlecom)

Jenny Rainbird, Head of EU Project Delivery at Inlecom Commercial Pathways, provided an overview of the Precinct project, an EU initiative addressing the protection of critical infrastructure in Europe. Launched in response to the 2018 call for safeguarding critical infrastructure from physical and cyber threats, Precinct aims to connect private and public stakeholders, first responders, and cities under a common cyber-physical security management approach.

The project focuses on tackling the increasing sophistication of attacks on critical infrastructure and the potential cascading effects on interconnected systems in smart cities. Precinct introduces coordination centers and digital twins as core concepts, aiming to harmonize emergency processes, share data, and use machine learning to enhance resilience.

With 40 partners involved, the two-year project, now in its 14th month, aims to establish an ecosystem platform for regions, fostering collaboration and effective security management. The project's outputs include a framework specification for critical infrastructure security, a collaborative cyber-physical security platform, a vulnerability assessment tool, and digital twins deployed in living labs across Europe. Key achievements in the first year include requirement specification, operational infrastructure development, prototype serious games, and a core digital twin reference.

As the project approaches its midway point, the team has delivered 13 milestones, participated in workshops and international events, and emphasized the importance of staying connected through the project's website and social media channels. The project is set to conclude in September of the following year.

PRAETORIAN: First Year Results & Highlights, Frederic Guyomard (EDF)

Frederic Guyomard discussed the objectives of developing resilience, particularly in the context of a new directive in Europe focusing on the resilience of critical entities. Projects like Present and Pretorian are at the forefront, adopting innovative approaches to address resilience needs. Collaboration with the European Commission is crucial, and the presentation aims to showcase their work, approaches, and activities in this domain.

The ambitious goal includes working with organizations addressing risks, such as those in the digital security domain. The emphasis is on developing tools to enhance resilience, demonstrated through projects like

PRAETORIAN. The project involves various stakeholders like developers, technological companies, users, academics, and First Responders across seven countries, with three pilots set to conclude in September next year.

The PRAETORIAN project's structure includes work packages on management, technical aspects, and tool development, covering areas like cybersecurity, physical security, and hybrid awareness. The presentation detailed their progress, deliverables, and the importance of addressing ethical and regulatory considerations. The focus on incident response and the development of decision support systems is highlighted.

Tools developed include those for cybersecurity and physical security awareness, utilizing AI and digital twins for modeling critical infrastructures. The interoperability platform facilitates data collection, aiding in the development of tools for crisis management. The presentation touched on simulated attacks, risk assessment approaches, and the upcoming demonstrations in Spain, Croatia, and France.

Specific use cases for the demonstrations were outlined, involving critical infrastructures like power plants, hospitals, and airports. The speaker also highlighted the project's engagement with the European Commission, addressing topics such as artificial intelligence and the social impact of their work.

The presentation concluded with an overview of the current status of tool development, nearing completion for validation. The next steps involve assessing the results, dissemination activities, and participation in related European projects.

Crisis Management: The Human Aspect of Critical Infrastructure Protection, Ms Nora Oufi, EDF

Nora Oufi, a PhD student at EDF, presented on Human Factors Applied to Cybersecurity, focusing on crisis management in hospitals during cyber attacks. She collaborated with Cyber experts from EDF on the PRAETORIAN project, examining the impact of a cyber attack on a hospital's human and organizational factors. The study aimed to understand vulnerabilities, improve prevention, contribute to crisis management, and integrate human factors into cybersecurity project designs. Using a systemic approach, they analyzed media articles, conducted empirical studies, interviews, and worked with Cyber experts to characterize different phases of a cyber crisis.

The study identified challenges faced by healthcare staff during cyber crises, such as loss of communication means, working in deteriorated conditions, and emotional impacts. Resilience factors included collective mobilization, medical expertise, and adaptability under pressure. Long-term effects included difficulties in reorganizing activities, implementing business continuity plans, and dealing with increased workload. Recommendations emphasized anticipating communication and resource loss, learning from cyber crises, clarifying the scope of surveillance, and establishing effective alert systems. Ongoing work involves further interviews, analyzing return on experience, and providing targeted recommendations for different departments in hospitals facing cyber attacks.

Q1) How easy is it for hospitals to fall back to “pen and paper” communication as was a recommendation from the experts?

A1) Working in deteriorated conditions is a critical aspect of crisis situations, raising questions about its effectiveness in crisis management. Despite uncertainties, the ability to adapt and continue activities, even through unconventional means like using paper and pen, reflects a form of resilience. Although not the ideal approach, the workforce demonstrated an innovative and adaptable mindset during the crisis, emphasizing the importance of finding solutions amid challenging circumstances.

In the context of healthcare, reliance on traditional tools such as paper and pen raises concerns about managing patient data in a digitalized world. The cyber threats associated with such situations further complicate the landscape, making it challenging to ascertain the depth and impact of an attack. The necessity to consider alternative methods, including reverting to paper, highlights the need for preparedness and training within the medical staff to ensure continuity in critical situations, emphasizing a human-centric approach to crisis response.

Q2) I am interested in the social and human input to cyber security, will your recommendations and findings be applicable to other fields ? (for example I work in public transport)?

A1) The PhD research focused on crisis management, particularly in the context of the COVID-19 crisis. The transversal recommendations are applicable to both COVID-19 and cyber crises but there is a need to be specific when considering sociological, psychological, and ergonomic aspects. The empirical studies, conducted in hospitals, involved engaging with staff to understand and tailor recommendations to the unique work situations. However, there has been collaboration with the National Railway company in France, showcasing a broader approach to crisis management, specifically in cybersecurity. The research extends beyond the health domain, as evidenced by their comparative study between crisis management in hospitals and the nuclear sector.

From Theory to Practice: Project Living Labs & Pilot Scenarios, Isabel Verwee, VIAS

Isabel introduced the living labs activity of the Precinct project, emphasizing its importance in bridging theory and practice. Work package five is dedicated to coordinating living labs, focusing on end-users, stakeholders, and project objectives, including validation, transferability, and measurement systems. The ambition is to enhance resilience, with specific KPIs and impact assessments. Living labs involve real-world contexts, innovation processes, co-creation, and a multi-methods research approach.

Dan Buchenhart from KU Leuven discussed their role in the Antwerp living lab, presenting a detailed physics-based dual drainage flood model. He highlighted the need for a data-driven model for real-time applications and short-term flood forecasting. Waterlink, a partner in the Antwerp living lab, shared insights into managing sewer systems and prioritizing projects based on data. They emphasized the value of the digital twin in gaining new insights and addressing challenges posed by climate change.

The presentation then shifted to the Athens living lab, focusing on resilience in transportation networks. Threat scenarios, involving cyber-physical attacks, technological accidents, and coordinated terrorist attacks, were outlined. The goal is to model interdependencies and quantify resilience through indicators. The process involves designing an interdependency graph, associating services, investigating indicators, and simulating attacks. The aspiration is to transition to a Knowledge Graph, enhancing data storage, accessibility, and automation for efficient decision-making during incidents.

KEMEA presented their coordination platform for linking Athens living labs' CI operators and stakeholders. The Center for Security Studies in Greece, acting as the national contact point for the European Commission on critical infrastructures, established a pilot coordination center to enhance collaboration between public and private sectors. Funded through the National Internal Security Fund, the center aims to facilitate continuous communication and information exchange, improving infrastructure security and fostering cooperation with First Responders agencies. The pilot center, incorporates incident reporting and provides risk maps and background data to critical infrastructures and First Responders. Successful tabletop exercises demonstrated its effectiveness, and the platform will be used in living lab scenarios for real-time incident coordination.

The GIS-based coordination center, with incident reporting and risk mapping capabilities, was developed to strengthen collaboration in Greece's critical infrastructure sector. Utilizing web-based technology, it allows users to visualize incidents on maps, apply filters, and access various layers of information. Successfully tested in remote and local exercises, the center is now set to demonstrate its effectiveness in the Athens region transport

resilience living lab. The goal is to provide near-real-time operational information during incidents, supporting stakeholder coordination. The presentation highlighted the center's role, capabilities, and upcoming tests in full-scale exercises.

Giuseppe Brancaccio from ITL presented the Bologna Living Lab which includes ITL, Bologna Airport, LEPIDA and FST technology which represent the railway operator.

The Living Lab has a focus on improving resilience in emergency situations, particularly during meteorological events like rainstorms and windstorms and aims to bridge the gap between different actors and improve communication and connectivity. The scenario definition and consolidation, along with the identification of priorities, were crucial initial steps. The process involves ongoing collaboration, periodic internal meetings, and data sharing with technical partners to ensure consistency with project expectations.

Giuseppe also emphasized the importance of public transport services as a bridge between telecommunication and transport networks. The goal is to optimize procedures for dealing with emergency situations while also seeking benefits in everyday life through the adaptation and recalibration of models.

Isabel summarised that the PRECINCT project has four living labs and three transferability demonstrators so the PRECINCT insights will also be transferred into demonstrators to obtain maximum value. The demonstrators are in Luxembourg, Ireland and Estonia.

PRAETORIAN Scenarios, Eva Munoz (ETRA I+D)

The PRAETORIAN project, a sister initiative to PRECINCT, focusing on enhancing the protection of critical infrastructures. The project aims to bridge the gap between theoretical concepts and practical implementation. PRAETORIAN offers an integrated platform and toolset for critical infrastructure operators, emphasizing situational awareness to anticipate, detect, and respond to cyber-physical security threats. Three pilot cases in Spain, France, and Croatia involve critical infrastructures in transport, energy, and health domains, showcasing the project's applicability in diverse settings.

The Spanish scenario in Valencia involves a cluster of critical infrastructures, including the port, airport, and hospital. The project integrates various sensors, cameras, and AI techniques for cyber and physical situation awareness. The system detects potential threats, such as cyber attacks, drone incursions, and explosions, illustrating cascading effects across interconnected infrastructures. The platform facilitates communication between operators and first responders, demonstrating the project's comprehensive approach to handling emergencies. The presenter also emphasizes the project's focus on integration, interoperability, usability, and usefulness.

Additionally, the speaker discusses the transferability and replicability of PRAETORIAN's solutions, aiming to adapt them to different critical infrastructures and domains across Europe. The project emphasizes an integrated system that can easily incorporate data from various sources, ensuring flexibility and adaptability. The ultimate goal is to validate and demonstrate the system in real-world scenarios, with the project set to run until September, contributing to the advancement of critical infrastructure protection and emergency response capabilities.

The French scenario is in the port of Bodo near Bordeaux. This region is crucial due to its scattered borders covering around 30 to 35 kilometers, distinguishing it from typical concentrated ports. The area is significant for a simulated attack involving a vital power plant supporting the region's electricity needs, along with a harbor and petroleum terminal, resembling various smaller ports. The attack simulation encompasses the refinery and petroleum location within the terminal port. The focus is on electronic and management system attacks,

involving an EDF building and targeting a transformer station between the port and a major power plant. The intention is not to shut down the power plant but to simulate threats.

The French use case involves strategic locations, disrupting radars, attacking the power plant, and showcasing tools for detection and response. The Spanish scenario, however, focuses on a hydropower plant and a hospital, emphasizing a cyber-physical attack and cascading effects. The second part involves a terrorist attempt to steal a dangerous biological sample from a biosafety level 3 laboratory and spread it at Zagreb airport, creating a potential pandemic.

The Croatian/Austrian pilot has a hydropower scenario which involves extensive preparation, a cyber attack on the plant, and physical destruction of floodgates, demonstrating the need for detection tools. In the biological threat scenario, terrorists target a laboratory and attempt a cyber attack to erase data before spreading a sample at an airport. PRAETORIAN tools help detect anomalies, coordinate responses, and mitigate the impact, involving counter-drone systems and collaboration between critical infrastructures. Both scenarios illustrate the importance of detection, coordination, and response tools to address complex and coordinated cyber-physical threats.

Q1) can you tell us what kind of pathogens are in a class 3 and a class 4?

A1) CORONA was class 3, Ebola is class 4. We are doing experiments with CORONA

Q2) there is a coordination centre that logs information, is this similar to KEMEA?

A1) Noone knows, there is a national authority that collects information from CI but the technical details are not publicly available.

PRECINCT Training & Capacity Building, Marisa Escalante (Technalia) Lorcan Connolly (RDS), Sandra Konig (AIT)The session was moderated by Marisa (Technalia) to present the PRECINCT project combined training We will have a short presentation on the cascading effects and then the Resilience Methodology Framework followed by interactive sessions.

In the context of projects like PRAETORIAN and PRECINCT, there is a recognized need to address issues arising from the interdependence of critical infrastructures. To evaluate and understand these interdependencies, a model has been developed, referred to as the interdependency graph. This graph is a high-level representation in which components are nodes, and edges depict dependencies, allowing for the analysis of cascading effects. The model distinguishes between physical and cyber components, utilizing a probabilistic milli automaton model to represent state changes. Notifications are transmitted between nodes to simulate interactions, reflecting changes in functionality or availability. The overall goal is to assess the cascading effects and enhance resilience. In practical application, the model is illustrated through a scenario of a flooding event affecting various aspects of a city, such as traffic, water, electricity, emergency services, and telecommunications. The focus is on understanding the impact on people, with the ultimate objective of minimizing their suffering and reducing overall societal impact. The approach involves combining cascading effect simulation and a resilience framework to learn from each other and improve overall preparedness and response strategies.

In the context of PRECINCT, a focus on resilience involves understanding and quantifying it for critical infrastructure systems. Resilience, stemming from risk assessment and acknowledging the entire disaster cycle, is measured by evaluating the services provided by infrastructure. These services, ranging from transport-related metrics like traffic delay to factors such as safety and electricity network availability, form the basis for assessing resilience. The time aspect is crucial, tracking service changes throughout different stages of events, encompassing pre-event, perturbation, and recovery phases. The developed framework defines critical infrastructure systems, quantifies services, and evaluates resilience as the percentage of service lost during cyber-physical hazards. This approach incorporates considerations for cyber hazards, deliberate disruptions, and

multimodal infrastructure within Precinct. The framework further employs resilience indicators, metrics, and a resilience index to set targets for enhancing resilience and guiding investment decisions over time.

In the theoretical example of the city of Numenor facing a flooding issue, the focus is on assessing and enhancing the resilience of its infrastructure system, encompassing urban transport, electricity, healthcare, and telecoms. A specific flooding event impacts various services, prompting the need for a resilient response from organizations such as local government and dispatching teams. The challenge lies in quantifying the service itself, with a key stakeholder interest in the safety of users. The resilience calculation involves valuing the service, modeling the hazard, and evaluating losses, primarily measured in terms of safety impact on users. The resilience index is determined by percentage losses in the original service. To enhance resilience, indicators such as flood protection measures, electricity failure warning systems, and emergency resource availability are considered. Costs associated with improving these indicators guide investment decisions to optimize resilience. The process also involves assigning relative weights to each indicator and setting targets based on cost-benefit analysis or return on investment metrics, ensuring a strategic allocation of resources for effective resilience enhancement.

Serious Games Meisam Gordan (University College Dublin)

Gamification is a game-based strategy aimed at engaging, motivating, and promoting learning in individuals. Serious Games are computer-based simulations combining knowledge and skill development with video game elements for active and problem-based learning. The key components of gamification, e-learning, video games, and serious games are explained, along with their applications across various sectors such as education, healthcare, government, and entertainment.

The value of serious games in critical infrastructure protection (CIP) is explored using an example of simulating flood events at the European scale. Preparedness and resilience is important in the face of life-threatening situations, showcasing how Serious Games serve as simulators for unseen events, offering experiential learning, immediate feedback, and cost-effective training. The Serious Game storyboard describes how players, including a director, defender, and attacker, interact with the system to make decisions and respond to simulated critical events. A prototype dashboard for post-game analytics is presented which is designed to assess players' performance and decision-making during serious game scenarios. The speaker highlights ongoing development efforts by a game development company, NURO, The presentation emphasizes the practical application of serious games in enhancing critical infrastructure protection through immersive and interactive simulations.

Q1) I was just wondering when you enter the role of the defender you said that it's an emergency responder with five years of experience, is it open-ended? how does that affect the game?

A1) We have different types of players, the years experience is used for their ranking, if the player has more experience the ranking is will be better. The game shows the experience and players results in the gameplay record.

Q2) I'm from Athens Airport. Is the Serious Game a kind of complex simulation ? I am confused with the concept of game theory.

A1) A serious game is a simulator of unseen events. From AIT we have game theory models and we want to compare the serious game with the game theoretical results.

In the workshop, Sandra presented an approach involving player feedback on their choices, emphasizing the need for intuitive actions. The current abstract graph representing system resilience was deemed unattractive, leading to the introduction of a more visually appealing representation. The cascading effect simulation focused on flooding threats, with nodes reacting to changes in states, triggering notifications to neighbors and creating a chain reaction. To improve, they proposed considering resilience indicators, allowing players to invest in components and visualize the impact on cascading effects.

The simulation involved establishing a baseline, representing the current situation without additional resilience measures. Investment strategies aimed to increase resilience, with the simulation providing feedback on the effectiveness of each choice compared to the baseline. Resilience was measured through indicators like tunnel protection, failure warning systems, and resource availability. The goal was to show players how their investments reduced the probability of severe damage.

In the exercise, participants prioritized enhancing tunnel protection and failure warning systems. Strategies were then assessed based on budget constraints and their impact on resilience. Two notable strategies emerged: one focusing on failure warning system improvement and another on maintaining tunnel resilience. The former showed a high return on investment, while the latter maximized resilience. Some strategies proved less effective, emphasizing the importance of evaluating both resilience and return on investment.

Q3 please can you explain the relationship between spending money and the indicators?

A1) While it is possible to spend money on enhancing resilience, the effectiveness varies. The best strategy for increasing resilience, in this case, focused on aspects unrelated to the tunnel, indicating that some investments might not directly impact resilience. The emphasis is on high Return on Investment (ROI) and considering factors such as people's well-being and potential cascading effects in failure scenarios, especially in critical systems like the failure warning system and power network.

standardization and policies in PRECINCT, Giacomo Bianchi (EOS)

The PRECINCT project aims to provide policy recommendations, support decision-making organizations, and assess the potential impact of a passive platform. This initiative plans to produce a white paper outlining a roadmap with required actions, policy recommendations, and best practices. The project focuses on three pillars: decision support, broad application, and target impact modelling. It incorporates EC strategies, security researchers, foreign working groups, and conferences. The project seeks cooperation with other EU initiatives like per volume and strategy, and standards are being established. Multiple outcomes include the creation of a working group, collaboration with international experts and projects, and the organization of technical events to build the mentioned white paper.

The Strategy Project, Pertti Woitsch (Woitsch Consulting)

In the STRATEGY project, the goal is to contribute to pre-standardization in crisis management by addressing the operational needs of practitioners. The project, initiated in September 2020 and funded by the European Commission, involves 23 partners from 14 countries, including national standardization bodies, public bodies, research organizations, and industry representatives. The project focuses on eight thematic areas, such as critical infrastructure protection, response planning, and early warning, aiming to enhance interoperability and effectiveness in crisis management.

To achieve these objectives, the project utilizes Centrelink Workshop Agreements (CWA) as a tool to bridge research and standardization. CWAs provide a flexible and efficient way to create agreements between stakeholders, allowing for faster collaboration and testing of standards. The project involves investigating standardization gaps, prioritizing them, and then implementing pre-standardization activities, including the creation of CWAs and technical specifications. Tabletop exercises and full-scale exercises are conducted to test and refine the standards in real-world scenarios. The project is making significant progress, and the findings from these exercises contribute to the continuous development of standards for effective crisis management.

PRAETORIAN Project Stanardisation efforts, Tamara Hadjina (Koncar Digital)

The PRAETORIAN project focuses on developing a tool to detect cyber-physical effects and facilitate coordinated responses among stakeholders, including end-users, critical infrastructure operators, and first responders. While standardization is an objective, the primary goal is tool development with an open architecture and standardized

interfaces to enable seamless data exchange among different system components. The project involves gathering input from end-users, such as critical infrastructure operators and first responders, to ensure the tool aligns with their needs and compliance standards. Notably, the project revealed a gap in existing risk assessment methodologies, prompting the development of a methodology that integrates cascading effects, enhancing information sharing and collaboration between end-users.

In addition to tool development, the project team is engaging with standardization efforts, particularly within ISO Committee 292, exploring potential collaborations with other projects. The project identified the importance of standardized data sharing and joined a Workshop Agreement initiated by the Strategic project to improve information processing in crisis management. Furthermore, the speaker, representing Concha, a company with over a century of experience in energy production and digital transformation, highlighted their commitment to standards, serving as national representatives in relevant working groups and emphasizing the significance of standards in ensuring interoperability and compliance with security measures, particularly in industrial control systems.

PRECINCT Standardisation Opportunities, Cristiano Passerini, LEPIDA

Cristiano highlighted an opportunity to lay the groundwork for future standardization, which could be beneficial not only for PRECINCT but also for the broader community. There are challenges faced in standardizing approaches, particularly in a living lab involving mobility and communication providers with diverse needs. The difficulty lies in aligning expectations, conducting gap analyses, and effectively communicating project outcomes. Cristiano shared his personal journey, emphasizing the need for a customized view to contribute meaningfully to standards. The complex nature of networks were discussed, drawing parallels with the hierarchical structure of communication networks versus the mesh structure of transportation networks. The concept of a "fire directive" was shared as a potential framework for standardization, focusing on the topological arrangement of networks and defining how producer and consumer nodes connect.

The constraints of sharing data across networks due to security concerns are acknowledged and a framework for standardization that involves careful consideration of data consumption and emphasizes the importance of understanding limitations in crisis management scenarios was proposed. The lack of standardization is acknowledged, and the utility of sharing developed scenarios is highlighted as a means to deepen understanding and potentially influence the establishment of standards for critical infrastructure in crisis situations. The overall narrative emphasizes the need for a nuanced, customized approach to standardization in the context of diverse network infrastructures and crisis management scenarios.

Q1) The presentations were interesting, I have been frustrated with the lengthy process of presenting papers to standardization groups. Please can you explain the CEN Workshop Agreements and whether they are likely to lead to established standards, particularly within the EU.

A1) It is important to effectively disseminating information. The challenge lies in communicating the project's existence and benefits. The initial target for utilization is within six organizations, each representing various practitioners such as medical and law enforcement. These practitioners contribute valuable insights based on real-life processes and data. While acknowledging the need for extensive dissemination efforts, word-of-mouth among practitioners and organizations, like Italian Firefighters with French and German counterparts, will play a crucial role. The eventual goal is to establish real standards, potentially involving collaboration with technical communities for standardization. The response also mentions existing semi-standards that serve as a basis for further development. Additionally, five standardization partners are involved in disseminating information and training.

Thoughts were shared on the intersection of physical, operational, and cyber security, particularly related to product producers and standards. The speaker suggests that the critical infrastructure domain should focus on enforcing standardization and highlights the challenge of integrating standards from different platforms. Another

speaker acknowledges the separation of domains in end users' perspectives and agrees that bridging the gap between physical and cyber security is crucial.

Reflections were made on the relationship between policy, standardization, and the challenges in the security environment. An emphasis was made on the slow pace of standardization, bureaucratic approaches to standards, and the need for organizations to be operationally prepared for dynamic security situations. The impact of directives and national laws on the standardization process should be noted, highlighting the disconnect between policy and the rapidly evolving security landscape.

There is an interdependence on the policy and standardization processes and it can be a challenge in the dynamic security environment to have a slow standardisation process. The bureaucratic nature of standards and their limitations in aiding organizations to adapt swiftly to security crises is challenging and there are difficulties related to legislation, regulation, and standards, along with the importance of their connection. The discussion touches on missed opportunities in 2018, concerns about data security, and the need for stronger European involvement in standardization efforts.

Conclusions of the Working Groups

Giacomo summarised the standardisation session. We had the working group session related to the standardization processes we had the pleasure to have three speakers from PRAETORIAN, PRECINCT and STRATEGY. This was the first step for a potential and future cooperation under this topic. We discussed about how we approached this topic in all three projects, our goals and how we intend to develop our strategies at European and National level. Thank you to all for the comments.

Marisa summarised the training session. We learned about the concepts of the Serious Game, Resilience methodical framework and the Interdependency graph and then had the opportunity to “play” with the some indicators and discuss the strategy to increase their resilience index and the return investment. We were not very good at this so we still need to learn more. Participants were asked to complete feedback forms on the training.

The working group for the PRAETORIAN tools was very interesting, it is challenging as the training courses take place in the mid of the of the project when the tools are at differing levels of maturity. However, it was valuable for the technical Partners and we now have more ideas about how to improve our tools tailored to the needs of the end users and the stakeholders and also how we can run even better training workshops.

The Numenor City – A vision of the future

Imagine there is a city today called Numenor. This city is flooded which has serious consequences on all kinds critical infrastructures including power networks, communication services impacting citizens and first responders. It also has a cascading effects on the emergency services and hospitals. Citizens cannot communicate, have no power in their homes and cannot travel. The City also becomes more vulnerable to opportunistic Cyber attacks.

I would like you to consider is a possible future of the same city and to do this I'd like to invite people that have seen the future are there and are sending you a postcard from that possible future where PRECINCT has been implemented in Numenor.

In the future, Numenor has implemented a comprehensive strategy to learn from past mistakes, particularly focusing on the interconnected nature of critical infrastructures (CIs). Recognizing them as an interconnected ecosystem, the rebuilding process involved not only reconstructing physical structures and streets but also incorporating information into critical infrastructure interdependency graphs. These graphs provide a comprehensive understanding of interactions between critical infrastructures, a crucial insight drawn from the

lessons of the past. Utilizing these interdependency graphs, Numenor has developed simulations and forecasts to anticipate the consequences of various events such as flooding, cyber attacks, or earthquakes. This proactive approach enables them not only to be prepared and trained for potential scenarios but also to enhance resilience by identifying areas for improvement and ensuring a more robust response to adverse events.

The exploration began by addressing contemporary global challenges such as climate change and the increasing reliance on digital systems. To comprehend and respond to these issues, a cascading effects simulation was developed. Recognizing the need to quantify resilience in the face of European Union directives, the precinct project emerged, yielding a resilience methodological framework. This framework employed the infrastructure's services to quantify its value and enhancements. By detailing the impact on people, transportation, and electricity systems, resilience was quantified, enabling the optimization of new enhancements. Resilience indicators were utilized to prioritize both resilience and investments, unveiling correlations and disparities. Innovative techniques were devised to prioritize solutions that optimized services, mitigating the consequences of cyber-physical threats. The journey also involved adapting to the influx of new data streams by developing a comprehensive framework and system.

The ambition is to have a Digital Twin which provides monitoring and simulations incorporating cascading effects. Where first responders are able to explore scenarios and propose mitigation actions.

Numenor, a smart city, utilizes a sophisticated IoT system with numerous sensors and actuators forming a critical infrastructure. The system employs a broker to collect data from sensors, such as temperature, and issue commands to actuators, like air conditioners, based on the collected data. To ensure the system's security and scalability, comprehensive testing is crucial. The platform features a real-time data recorder for testing datasets, a mobile phone data generator capable of simulating cyber attacks, and a flexible simulation sensor model supporting various configurations. This toolset enables testing under different conditions, including the evaluation of worker limits, potential security breaches, and scalability issues. Additionally, the platform supports continuous integration and continuous delivery, providing an efficient and cost-effective solution for testing diverse scenarios.

In the futuristic city of Numenor, residents rely on the Unified Present Situational Awareness User Interface, commonly known as the Dashboard, to manage data from the PRECINCT Ecosystem Platform. This interface serves as a centralized hub where real-time information is collected, allowing for the assessment of infrastructure status and prompt responses to threats or adverse events such as flooding. The Dashboard integrates widgets for data visualization, offering a comprehensive view of the city's conditions. Through simulations displayed on the Dashboard, officials can monitor and predict the empirical infrastructure's response to potential threats, enabling proactive decision-making. The system was particularly useful during a recent flooding incident in Numenor, where the simulation showcased the progressive collapse of the electrical grid, traffic, and mobile telecom networks. This visual representation aids in developing effective strategies for mitigating the impact of future incidents.

The Serious Game tool is a very economical way to train the operator on scenarios and prepare for attacks or events. Access is limited to validated stakeholders. The dashboard allows the user to gain a analysis insights so far it contains 50 different scenarios.

Numenor, the fictitious city, is well-equipped with a comprehensive set of tools, smoothly operated and configured by smart IT professionals. This success is attributed to lessons learned from the PRECINCT project, living labs, and studying various risk aspects in deploying tools. The project utilizes a formal description for deploying tools and services, focusing on cloud, on-premises, or hybrid installations. The chosen standard is Oasis Tosca, emphasizing readable documents for both humans and machines, facilitating automated deployment and configuration. This approach allows for the description of services, tool deployment, coordination, and

adaptation across different cities. The use of a computer-readable standard ensures a common language and aids in standardization across cities. Containerization and orchestration are crucial components, enabling adaptability and reusability from one city to another. Thanks to these measures, Numenor is well-prepared with operational tools to effectively respond to potential attacks. This is a virtual City but everything you've seen here is based on real work that's happening in the PRECINCT project.

The day closed on a message of hope for continued collaboration between the projects.

Organisational Aspects

The 2nd SEW demonstrated an improvement over the first, especially considering the increase in the number of participants in the workshop. Due to the ambitious Key Performance Indicator (KPI) that was attached to the PRECINCT Conference (180 participants), the goal was to continue this trend of increased participation. The success of this co-organisation paved the way not only to reach the liaison and cooperation activities outlined in the early stages of the project, but also to increase the engagement of stakeholders. Within this context, PRECINCT partners decided to continue the PRECINCT conference effort and reached out H2020/Europe projects relevant to PRECINCT and included them in the organisation process.

In terms of content, the interactive formats were kept, but the increased account of co-organising parties allowed them to organise their own parallel sessions.

4.3 PRECINCT Conference

The PRECINCT Conference took place in Brussels on May 16 and 17, 2023, and was organized with the participation of 7 other H2020 and Horizon Europe projects as follows:

- AI4CYBER
- EU-CIP
- EU-HYBNET
- PRAETORIAN
- DYNABIC
- STRATEGY
- SUNRISE.

The goal of the conference was to bring together a large audience of CI stakeholders, including researchers, industry, civil society, policy-makers, etc.. It was also the first PRECINCT organised event in the second year of the project and allowed partners to present an update of the work undertaken so far. To avoid duplication of the previous events, the Conference agenda focused on more high-level and cross-cutting issues, such as countering hybrid threats, innovation uptake and EU legislation/directives on protecting Critical Infrastructure (e.g. CER & NIS2), whereas it provided several follow-ups for some PRECINCT outputs, including the PRECINCT training and capacity building programme, the standardisation and policy recommendation activities, and the Living Labs (LLs). Moreover, some space was given to the participating projects in the form of break-out sessions or short presentations on topics related to PRECINCT. This approach provided various benefits, including a larger audience encompassing stakeholders from the other projects, a wider scope for the discussion, and an exchange of ideas and approaches. As with previous events, the PRECINCT Conference received positive feedback and a great number of registrants. At this event, there was a KPI of 180 participants, and there were 177 registrations before the event with various in-person registrations the day of. Overall, a great number of different stakeholders were involved, as depicted in figure 4.5. Even though a large portion of participants were PRECINCT partners, many other types of stakeholders took part in the event as well, such as Critical Infrastructure Operators, Academia & Research and Industry & Technology Providers.

Figure 4-5: Stakeholders Registered to the PRECINCT Conference³

Figure 4-6: Image from the PRECINCT Conference

³ Certain registrants selected multiple groups, only the first one selected was used

4.3.1 Takeaways Learned

The PRECINCT Conference further demonstrated the value of tying in the liaison and cooperation activities into the stakeholder events in order to increase engagement. The KPI of 180 participants was met, and the feedback received from participants at the conclusion of the event was very positive.

The more general focus of the Conference led to the discussions focusing on PRECINCT-related topics instead of only on the work of the project; therefore, for the final event, instead of inviting projects and stakeholders to be a part of the agenda, the decision was made to have them join as participants. This would allow for the Final Event to really focus on PRECINCT outputs and act as a commercial event, which is its main objective.

4.4 PRECINCT Final Event

On September 14th, 2023, the PRECINCT Final Event took place in Bologna at the headquarter of the Emilia-Romagna Region. The objective was to run a commercial event where all of the tools and assets developed within the project's lifespan were presented to a large and relevant CI stakeholder audience. 111 people participated, with around half participating online. The event involved numerous partners of the PRECINCT project and some stakeholders directly involved in the project activities. The following stakeholders were present at the Final Event:

- Marconi Express (MEX) → MEX is the service provider of the connection between the airport and Bologna Centrale railway station. The people mover was central for the design of the LL4 and the tools of the PRECINCT Framework, so the CEO and the operative manager attended the Final Event to observe the project outputs;
- TPER → TPER is the urban mobility provider of numerous cities in the Emilia-Romagna region including the Metropolitan City of Bologna. TPER was also directly involved in the design of the LL4 and the Final Event was an opportunity to observe the outputs and possible future implementations within the LL4 PRECINCT Framework.
- Emilia-Romagna Region → It is the public body that deals with the management of the entire Region. The PRECINCT Final Event involved figures who deal with the management of the territory and transport within the regional territory, and who also deal with the monitoring and management of the security of the digital and physical infrastructures present in the region. For this reason, it was an opportunity of great interest to deepen the results of the PRECINCT Project.

The event received very positive feedback both during the course and at the end of the event. The aspects that were most successful were the contents presented, which retraced through the technical outputs two years of project, and the organization of the event, which allowed the presence of a large audience in presence and remotely throughout the course of the event. Overall, the PRECINCT Final Event was a special opportunity to visualize all the results obtained in two years of joint work and new synergies created, giving the opportunity to those who have not been directly involved in the project, to fully understand the objectives and results obtained by the PRECINCT Consortium.

Figure 4-7: Image from the PRECINCT Final Event

4.5 Assessment of the PRECINCT Events

The main objectives of the PRECINCT events were to consolidate and present the main outputs of PRECINCT and ensure a strong interaction with industry CI stakeholders, end-users, citizens, solutions providers, and broad CI academia interest groups. All events were organised to demonstrate to stakeholders the progress of the work undertaken during the project's lifespan and triggered feedback opportunities. The space between the different events allowed stakeholders to provide feedback at critical points of the project, maximising the impact they could have on the project and vice versa. Regarding the content, the feedback received about the events was always quite positive, with participants finding the content quite relevant and worth their time.

One of the main drawbacks of the PRECINCT events was the lack of consistency in the classification used for stakeholders in the registration form. The selections did not reflect the categories of stakeholders that were outlined in the Grant Agreement (GA) in a 1:1 way. Instead, Law Enforcement Agencies (LEAs) were divided into First Responders, Students from Academia and Research, and General Industry Consultants from Industry and Technology Providers, as described in a different section of the GA. This slightly affected the analysis of the present and most relevant stakeholders; nevertheless, it did not impact the project in a significant way as the main stakeholder groups were still represented (even if they were split). Additionally, this issue was rectified for the PRECINCT Final event registration form. In terms of external stakeholders, First Responders (including LEAs) covered on average 8% of participants in events, while Critical Infrastructure Operators and CIP protection actors covered on average 31% of participants. Despite not being ideal, as the targeted stakeholders did not represent the majority of stakeholders present, it is important to note that PRECINCT includes 40 partners, encompassing many First Responders and Critical Infrastructure Operators which increases the number of present targeted stakeholders within the events. In addition, the two stakeholder categories represent a great number of attendees. Eventually, it shall be noted that there was an increase in all events from stakeholders.

Overall, the PRECINCT events were quite successful, as there was a general increase in attendance for each event, and a wealth of knowledge created by the project was shared with stakeholders during the events' execution. Furthermore, the events attracted a wide range of relevant stakeholders, as shown in the previous figures' graphs, which was the main objective of these events. Additionally, these activities built a considerable part of the Stakeholder Needs Knowledge Base, as all of the events were recorded and uploaded on the PRECINCT YouTube channel. This will allow the events to continue to have an impact even after the PRECINCT project finishes.

5 Cyber-Physical Security Stakeholder Needs Knowledge Base

A main output of WP6 was to create a Stakeholder Needs Knowledge Base for stakeholders to be able to refer to after the conclusion of the PRECINCT events, and the project per se, for knowledge and outputs created by PRECINCT. There are three main repositories where stakeholders can refer to this PRECINCT knowledge: the PRECINCT website, the PRECINCT YouTube Channel, and a PRECINCT Zenodo Community. Together these make up the Stakeholder Needs Knowledge Base; however, the main knowledge base is considered the Zenodo community, as it hosts most of the PRECINCT's knowledge, including what can be found in the other two.

5.1 The PRECINCT Website

[The PRECINCT website](#) was created by VIAS in November 2021 (M3 of the project) and was the first PRECINCT knowledge repository. The website allowed for stakeholders to gain awareness about the project, learn of its objectives and stay up to date of further activities, including all of the events organised by PRECINCT.

Structured in seven sections, the website provides:

- A general presentation of the project scope and ambitions, and the milestones of the project. and the last updates.
- A presentation of the key outputs of the project and the (management) structure.
- An overview of the Consortium partners.
- A description of the four Living Labs, their scenario and CIs.
- PRECINCT publication material (videos, training session, articles, promotional material and newsletters).
- An overview of events organised by PRECINCT and third-party events and of the other projects in the European Cluster for Securing Critical Infrastructures.
- A contact form (redirecting to the project PM, ICP).

On the homepage, an insert is dedicated to the last updates of announcements about the project (“newsletter publication”, “event subscription”, ...). VIAS is responsible of the website creation (content and layout) and the maintenance and updates. The website will be kept online minimum in the three months following the end of the project (and probably for the next three years). The website was submitted to ethics review at M3, and validated.

Figure 5-1: Overview of the website

5.2 The PRECINCT YouTube Channel

The [PRECINCT YouTube channel](#) was created by EOS in May 2022 following the conclusion of the 1st SEW, using the PRECINCT project email. The YouTube channel serves as a tool where stakeholders or project partners could watch or rewatch the PRECINCT workshops if they were unable to attend the workshop or missed certain parts. Following the uploading of the workshop, other videos were uploaded to the channel, such as an innovation lesson and the general project video, letting stakeholders engage with content outside of simply the PRECINCT events. At the time of writing the deliverable, PRECINCT has a total of 14 subscribers and 6 videos, with the most watched video being the 2nd SEW recording with 147 views. Below is a image from the YouTube Channel and its analytics.

D6.1 PRECINCT CyberPhysical Security Stakeholder Needs Knowledge Base - Liaison and cooperation

Figure 5-2: Youtube Channel Overview

Figure 5-3: Youtube Channel Analytics

Figure 5-4: Youtube Channel Analytics (continued)

The analytics were taken from period of 20/06/2023-17/07/2023 and demonstrate that even in between periods of uploads there seems to be some level of engagement with the PRECINCT videos. Additionally, the average watch time is 2.1 hours, which indicates that viewers are spending a considerable amount of time watching the videos instead of clicking away immediately. After the conclusion of the project, the YouTube Channel will remain open for stakeholders to come back to rewatch the PRECINCT events and the innovation lesson to refresh themselves whenever needed, as there is no upkeep needed to maintain the channel.

5.3 The PRECINCT Zenodo Community

Figure 5-5: Overview of the Zenodo Community

Zenodo is a general-purpose open repository developed under the European OpenAIRE program and operated by CERN. It allows researchers to deposit research papers, data sets, research software, reports, and any other research. [PRECINCT opened its own community](#) in April, 2023 in order to start curating all of the mature tools, publications and other resources. Due to the very restrictive nature of the project, not many of the deliverables will be published in the Community; however, all of the public deliverables, scientific articles, videos, presentations, publications, etc. produced by the project will be considered. Namely, the Zenodo community will house most of the PRECINCT-produced content available to the public, including some of which is already found on the YouTube Channel and the website. Due to the open access of Zenodo, any type of stakeholder will be able to engage with the content, while it may potentially attract more academia and research stakeholders due to the research-oriented nature of the site. In addition, the longevity of the results will be guaranteed due to Zenodo's support from CERN and the European Union, guaranteeing that the impact will be long-lasting.

5.4 Assessment of the PRECINCT Stakeholder Needs Knowledge Base

The main objective of the Stakeholder Needs Knowledge Base is to share the project findings to a great number of relevant CI stakeholders across the EU. By collating almost all knowledge (the exception refers to the EU restricted materials) generated by PRECINCT and publishing them on an open-access repository like Zenodo, PRECINCT is ensuring that the knowledge will outlive the project itself. Additionally, it is important that the knowledge can be easily found and can be easily accessible to stakeholders in order to decrease any barriers to engagement. Thus, the Stakeholder Needs Knowledge Base of PRECINCT aims to be as open as possible and as simple as possible, by using well-known platforms and ensuring that the platforms complement each other. YouTube is one of the world's most recognizable video-hosting platforms, allowing stakeholders to easily interact with PRECINCT's video content and even sharing it to other stakeholders. In addition, the channel has been advertised on the website, social media channels and at the final event, thus, stakeholder awareness should be high. Zenodo is also well-known, especially in the European research community, as a knowledge repository. It is also quite easy to use, and once the PRECINCT community is located the content is enlisted by the date uploaded in an easy-to-read format. These two platforms are free for the PRECINCT project to use and maintain, meaning that the lifespan of these depends on the platform's existence (currently there is no foreseeable closing of either platform). Therefore, if the PRECINCT website becomes defunct, all knowledge will still remain on Zenodo and YouTube.

As it stands, the PRECINCT Stakeholder Needs Knowledge Base achieves its objective of providing stakeholders with an open access library that contains the projects' findings allowing them to enter after the conclusion of the project. The knowledge base has not only benefited the stakeholders by providing them with knowledge created by the PRECINCT research; it also benefits PRECINCT by continuously raising awareness of the project and by allowing stakeholders to hopefully exploit this knowledge to increase CIs resilience. Additionally, by using the knowledge of stakeholder needs gained through engagement with stakeholders in the PRECINCT events, the knowledge base and T6.3, the potential for uptake of PRECINCT tools and assets should increase as stakeholders understand the tools, how they work, and why they matter to protecting Europe's CI.

6 Liaison & Cooperation Activities

PRECINCT engaged in various Liaison and Cooperation Activities aiming to share and benefit from the knowledge of other projects and initiatives in the domain of CIP. The first and foremost activity in this domain was PRECINCT joining the European Cluster for Securing Critical Infrastructure (ECSCI) in 2021. This cluster creates synergies and fosters emerging disruptive solutions to security issues via cross-projects collaboration and innovation, while also highlighting the different approaches between the clustered projects and establishing tight and productive connections with closely related and complementary H2020 projects. PRECINCT was present at the second workshop organised on April 27-29, 2022 both presenting the project and coordinating a panel on standard in CI. This first step led to the stable participation of PRECINCT to the working group “Contribution to standards and regulations on the protection of Critical Infrastructures”. PRECINCT was also present at the “1st annual conference on Critical Infrastructure Protection and ECSCI workshop” held on the 20th and 21st September in Brussels. PRECINCT also worked in collaboration with the ECSCI cluster and other projects in the CI area to organise a Workshop to be held on December 5, 2023 on “Collaborative Standardisation and Policy making for greater resilience in Europe”. This workshop will be held after the completion of the PRECINCT project but it remains useful to be present with the aim to share results and lessons learned from the project. PRECINCT’s participation in these events allowed the project to further promote PRECINCT and disseminate its project results to stakeholders and invited the cluster to participate in each of its events. On top of the above participation PRECINCT has also worked closely with the EU-CIP project which will be transforming the ECSCI cluster into a an EU-wide knowledge network with advanced analytical and innovation support capabilities, of which PRECINCT envisages to be a part of.

Figure 6-1: Visualisation of the ECSCI

PRECINCT also cooperated directly with projects that were of close relevance to it, most notably its sister project PRAETORIAN and the STRATEGY Project. PRAETORIAN and STRATEGY have been involved in all PRECINCT events, with PRAETORIAN co-organising the 2nd Stakeholder Workshop and the PRECINCT Conference, and STRATEGY participating in the standardization and policy recommendations sessions for the SEWs, while also being co-organisers for the PRECINCT Conference. Furthermore, PRECINCT and STRATEGY signed a memorandum of cooperation (see Annex V) outlining the areas for further cooperation and the activities to be undertaken, including the use of a STRATEGY Standard in the Athens Living Lab. KEMEA led the CEN workshop addressing the efficiency and accuracy of Incident Situational Reporting for Critical Infrastructures in the context of the STRATEGY project as a continuation of KEMEA's activities in the field of Critical Infrastructure Protection and development of the pilot Coordination Center for Critical Infrastructure Protection. The incident reporting form produced in the specific CWA was presented during the PRECINCT Athens LL demo as part of the H3CIP demo, and the incident fields filled out through the form based on the Athens threat scenario were visualized through the H3CIP. The functionality of the H3CIP as well as the incident reporting form were evaluated by the system's intended end users, and relevant feedback for the usability and usefulness for the form was collected by the participating end users. More information regarding this cooperation can be found in D6.5 "Impact Assessment and Policy & Standardisation Recommendations"

7 Conclusions

Although the PRECINCT project did not develop a traditional Dissemination & Communication Plan, it managed to engage stakeholders throughout the project's lifespan. The main engagement was through its stakeholder knowledge base task (supplemented by dissemination communication tasks under T6.2) under which PRECINCT partners created the knowledge base repositories and organized the 4 main events to gather external stakeholders. As previously mentioned, the project events were at critical points of the project which delivered feedback that was considered during the project's development progress and continuously informing stakeholders for the corresponding updates.

In terms of meeting its objectives, the PRECINCT project managed to consolidate and present the main outputs of PRECINCT and to ensure a strong interaction with industry CI stakeholders, end-users, citizens, solutions providers, and broad CI academia interest groups, which was the central aim of Task 6.1. In addition, all events outlined in the Grant Agreement (GA) were held and managed to reach any KPI attached to them.

Finally, one of the main outputs of this task was a CyberPhysical Security Stakeholder Needs Knowledge Base that allows the PRECINCT generated knowledge to be easily accessible to stakeholders beyond the project's lifespan. This was achieved with the creation of the PRECINCT Zenodo community, which houses all publicly available PRECINCT information for free, complemented by the YouTube Channel and the website.

8 Annex

8.1 PRECINCT 1st SEW Agenda

Agenda

PRECINCT's 1st Stakeholders Engagement Workshop

Maison des Associations Internationales, Rue Washington 40, 1050 Brussels (Ixelles)
(On-Line, Zoom)

5th May 2022

08:30 – 09:00	<i>Welcome and Registration</i>	
09:00 – 09:10	Remarks	Jenny Rainbird, Project Coordinator (ICP)
09:10 – 09:25	Main Key Results and Roadmap	Gabriele Giunta (ENG)
09:25 – 09:50	BluePrints and Knowledge Graphs	Djibrilla Amadou-Kountche (AKKA), Stathis Zavvos (VLTN)
09:50 – 10:10	Serious Games	Daniel McCrum (UCD), Yash Shekhawat (NURO)
10:10 – 10:30	PRECINCT Architecture and Implementation	David Vermeir (IMEC)
10:30 – 10:45	Coffee Break	
10:45 – 11:00	PRECINCT Living Labs	Shirley Delannoy (VIAS)
11:00 – 11:15	Operation Athens	John Limaxis, Gerasimos Kouloumbis (ICP)
11:15 – 11:30	Operation Antwerp	Shirley Delannoy (VIAS)
11:30 – 11:45	Operation Ljubljana	Denis Čaleta (ICS)
11:45 – 12:00	Operation Bologna	Giuseppe Brancaccio (ITL)
12:00 – 12:40	Partners' feedback on the business requirements	Mark Bennett (ICP)
12:40 – 12:45	Morning Conclusion	Jenny Rainbird, Project Coordinator (ICP)
12:45 – 13:30	Lunch Break	
13:30 – 13:45	Critical Infrastructure Protection	Päivi Mattila, EU-HYBNET Project Coordinator (LAUREA) <i>Moderator:</i> Mark Miller (CPT)
13:45 – 15:15	PRECINCT's Future Technical Aspects	<i>Speakers:</i> Daniel McCrum (UCD), Stefan Lefever (IMEC), Stefan Schauer (AIT), Gabriele Giunta (ENG), Lorcan Connolly (RDS)
15:15 – 15:30	Coffee Break	
15:30 – 16:45	Drivers and Barriers for implementation of new CIP Solutions	<i>Moderator:</i> Mark Bennett (ICP) <i>Speakers:</i> Marisa Escalante Martinez (TCNL), Päivi Mattila (LAUREA), Vito Morreale (ENG), Benoit Baurens (AKKA), Denis Čaleta (ICS)
16:45 – 17:00	Conclusions	Jenny Rainbird, Project Coordinator (ICP)

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8.2 PRECINCT 2nd SEW Agenda

PRECINCT's 2nd Stakeholder Engagement Workshop

Co-organized with the help of PRAETORIAN

AGENDA

Time	Topic	Room in the M.A.I
8:50 – 9:00	Welcome and Registration	Berlin Room
9:00 – 9:10	Opening of the Workshop	Berlin Room
9.10 – 9.20	PRECINCT: First Year Results & Highlight	Berlin Room
9.20 – 9.40	PRAETORIAN: First Year Results & Highlight	Berlin Room
9:40 – 10:30	Crisis Management: The Human Aspect of Critical Infrastructure Protection	Berlin Room
10:30 – 10:45	Coffee Break	
10:45 – 13.00	From Theory to Practice: Project Living Labs & Pilot Scenarios	Berlin Room
13.00 – 13.45	Lunch Break	
13.45 – 15.15	Working Group #1: Standardisation & Policy Recommendations	Paris Room
13.45 – 15.15	Working Group #2: PRECINCT Training & Capacity Building	Berlin Room
13.45 – 15.15	Working Group #3: PRAETORIAN Training & Capacity Building	Roma Room
15.15 – 15.30	Coffee Break	
15:30 – 16:00	Conclusions of the Working Groups	Berlin Room
16:00 – 17.00	PRECINCT: A Perspective in View of Exploitation (Q&A)	Berlin Room
17.00 – 17.15	Conclusions & Closing of the Workshop	Berlin Room

8.3 PRECINCT Conference Agenda

PRECINCT Conference

on

Critical Infrastructure Protection, Cybersecurity and Crisis Management

Day 1 – May 16th

AGENDA

Time	Topic	Speaker
9:00 – 9:30	Welcome and Registration	PRECINCT Consortium
9:30 – 10:00	Opening of the Conference	Ms. Natalja Miolato , <i>Project Advisor at the Research Executive Agency</i>
10:00 – 11:00	Protecting Critical Infrastructures facing Hybrid Threats	Chair: Dr. Stefan Schauer , <i>Senior Researcher for Security & Communication Technologies at AIT</i> Speakers: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dr. Päivi Mattila, <i>Director of Security Research Program & EU-HYBNET project coordinator</i> • Gilda de Marco, <i>R&D - European Projects at Insiel</i> • Rafa Company, <i>Director of Safety and Security at Valencia Port</i>
11:00 – 11:15	Audience Q&A	Dr. Stefan Schauer , <i>Senior Researcher for Security & Communication Technologies at AIT</i>
11:15 – 11:30	EU-CIP: a novel pan European knowledge network for Resilient Infrastructures.	Dr. Gabriele Giunta , <i>Head of the Smart Transport and Infrastructures Unit with the IS3 R&D Lab at ENGINEERING</i>
<i>Coffee break</i>		
11:45 – 12:45	Living Lab Methodology - Innovative Threat Response	Mrs. Shirley Delannoy , <i>Researcher, VIAS Institute</i> Thomas de Meester , <i>Innovation Specialist/Product Owner, IMEC</i>
12:45 – 13:00	Audience Q&A	Mrs. Shirley Delannoy , <i>Researcher, VIAS Institute</i>
<i>Lunch break</i>		
13:45 – 14:00	Practical Information on the Break-Out Sessions	Dr. Giovanni Nisato , <i>Managing Director & Founder of Innovation Horizons; Inlecom Commercial Pathways</i>

PRECINCT

14:00 – 15:30	Break-out session #1: Cybersecurity Datasets: Challenges and Opportunities	Dr. Erkuden Rios, <i>Director of Cybersecurity R&I projects at TECNALIA/Coordinator of AI4CYBER</i>
	Break-out session #2: Critical Infrastructure Resilience through Public Transport	Mrs. Carmela Canonico, <i>Safety & Security Manager at UITP</i>
	Break-out session #3: PRECINCT's 2nd Training & Capacity Building Programme	Mrs. Marisa Escalante, <i>Project Manager at TECNALIA</i>
<i>Coffee break</i>		
15:45 – 17:15	Break-out session #4: Standardization in PRECINCT & STRATEGY and future policy recommendations	Mrs. Loredana Mancini, <i>PRECINCT Impact Manager</i> Dr. Georgios Sakkas, <i>Research Associate at KEMEA</i>
	Break-out session #5: Validation of security tools for CI protection	Mr. Tim Stelkens-Kobsch, <i>Aviation Security Researcher at DLR,</i> Mrs. Eva Muñoz Navarro, <i>Project Manager at Grupo Etra</i>
	Break-out session #6: PRECINCT's 2nd Training & Capacity Building Programme	Mrs. Marisa Escalante, <i>Project Manager at TECNALIA</i>
17:15 – 17:30	Conclusions – End of Day 1	Dr. Giovanni Nisato, <i>Managing Director & Founder of Innovation Horizons; Inlecom Commercial Pathways</i>

Day 2 – May 17th

AGENDA

Time	Topic	Partner Responsible
8:30 – 9:00	Welcome and Registration	PRECINCT Consortium
9:00 – 9:15	Opening of Day 2	Dr. Giovanni Nisato, <i>Managing Director & Founder of Innovation Horizons; Inlecom Commercial Pathways</i>
9:15 – 9:30	Keynote speech	Mr. Giannis Skiadareisis, <i>Area Coordinator for Strengthened Security Research and Innovation (SSRI), DG HOME</i>
9:30 – 10:30	Panel Discussion on Innovation Uptake for Critical Infrastructure Protection	Chair: Mr. Mark Miller, <i>CEO of Conceptivity & Vice-Chair of EOS</i> Speakers: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mr. Giannis Skiadareisis, <i>Area Coordinator for Strengthened Security Research and Innovation (SSRI), DG HOME</i>

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dr. Takis Katsoulakos <i>Managing Director for Inlecom Commercial Pathways (TBC)</i> • Mr. Isto Mattila <i>R&D Director at Laurea University of Applied Sciences & CEO of Dicitur Ltd</i> • Dr. Giovanni Nisato <i>Managing Director & Founder of Innovation Horizons; Inlecom Commercial Pathways</i>
10:30 – 10:45	Audience Q&A	Mr. Mark Miller , <i>CEO of Conceptivity & Vice-Chair of EOS</i>
<i>Coffee Break</i>		
10:45 – 11:45	The Resilience of Critical Entities: a New EC Directive	Chair: Dr. Georgios Sakkas , <i>Research Associate at KEMEA</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dr. Erkuden Rios, <i>Director of Cybersecurity R&I projects at TECNALIA; Coordinator of AI4CYBER</i> • Dr. Aikaterini Poustourli, <i>Scientific Fellow of STRATEGY; Satways Ltd.)</i> • Mr. Paolo Venturoni, <i>CEO of the European Organisation for Security</i>
11:45 – 12:30	Resilience in Cybersecurity	Dr. Sandra König , <i>Scientist/Researcher in Safety and Security at AIT</i>
12:30 – 13:00	After PRECINCT, DYNABIC	Dr. Erkuden Rios , <i>Director of Cybersecurity R&I projects at TECNALIA</i>
13:00 – 13:10	Closing of the Conference	Dr. Giovanni Nisato , <i>Managing Director & Founder of Innovation Horizons</i>

8.4 PRECINCT Final Event Agenda

PRECINCT Final Event

9:00 – 17:00 CEST, September 14th, 2023
Viale della Fiera, 8 - 40127, Bologna, Italy

AGENDA

<u>Time</u>	<u>Topic</u>	<u>Speaker</u>
8:30 – 9:00	Welcome and Registration	The Institute for Transport and Logistics (ITL)
9:00 – 9:10	Opening of the Final Event	Mr. Guido Fabbri , <i>President of ITL</i>
9:20 – 9:30	Objectives and ambitions of PRECINCT	Mrs. Jenny Rainbird , <i>Head of EU Project Delivery at ICP; PRECINCT Project Coordinator</i>
9:30 – 10:00	Quick Overview of PRECINCT's Achievements & Success stories	Mr. Gabriele Giunta , <i>Head of the Smart Transport and Infrastructures Unit at ENGINEERING</i>
10:00 – 10:45	Demonstration of the PRECINCT Tools & Assets: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cascading Effects Simulation • Resilience Methodological Framework <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cyber Range 	Mr. Manuel Egger , <i>Junior Research Engineer at AIT</i> Mr. Lorcan Connolly , <i>Director at Research Driven Solutions</i> Mrs. Marisa Escalante , <i>Project Manager at TECNALIA</i>
<i>Coffee Break</i>		
11:00 – 11:45	Demonstration of the PRECINCT Tools & Assets: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Serious Games • Supporting IT operation : Blueprints as guidelines and executable plans for mastering deployment, configuration and maintenance of PRECINCT Tools 	Dr. Páraic Carroll , <i>Assistant Professor in Transport Engineering at UCD</i> Dr. Djibrilla Amadou Kountche , <i>R&D Project Manager at AKKODIS Research</i>
11:45 – 12:30	The Roadmap to Implementation: View from the Transferability Demonstrators	Mrs. Shirley Delannoy , <i>Researcher, VIAS Institute</i> Mrs. Esther Linask , <i>Geoinformatics specialist at Tallinn Strategic Management Office</i> Dr. Seifeddine Bettaieb , <i>Researcher at Luxembourg Institute of Science and Technology</i>
<i>Lunch Break</i>		

13:30 – 14:30	Bologna Living Lab – Experiences, Lessons Learned and What Next?: PRECINCT Analytics Dashboard and Digital Twin	Mr. Nicola Durante, <i>Research And Development Engineer at ENGINEERING</i>
14:30 – 14:45	Keynote Speech: Policy & Critical Infrastructure Protection	Dr. Aikaterini Poustourli, <i>Scientific Fellow of STRATEGY; Satways Ltd.)</i>
14:45 – 15:15	PRECINCT Recommendations: PRECINCT White Book; Policy Recommendations	Mrs. Loredana Mancini, <i>PRECINCT Impact Manager</i>
Coffee Break		
15:30 – 17:00	After PRECINCT: Upscaling Potential	Chair: Dr. Giovanni Nisato, <i>Managing Director & Founder of Innovation Horizons; Inlecom Commercial Pathways</i> Dr. Cristiano Passerini, <i>COO Digital Innovation Hub - Emilia-Romagna at Lepida ScpA</i> Mr. Benoit Baurens, <i>Head of Innovation Department and R&D Program Manager at AKKODIS</i> Mr. Pedro Homem de Gouveia, <i>Senior Policy and Project Manager, Governance & Integration + Safety & Security at Polis Network</i>
17:00 – 17:15	Conclusion of PRECINCT's Final Event	Mrs. Jenny Rainbird, <i>Head of EU Project Delivery at ICP; PRECINCT Project Coordinator</i>

8.5 Memorandum of Cooperation between PRECINCT & STRATEGY

Editors

Name	Contact	Entity
Jenny Rainbird	Inlecom Commercial Pathways (ICP)	Edits to MOU objectives
Giannis Chasiotis	Satways Ltd.	Edits to MOU objectives

Contributors

Name	Entity	Contribution
Jenny Rainbird	Inlecom Commercial Pathways (ICP)	PRECINCT project outline
Giannis Chasiotis	Satways Ltd.	STRATEGY project outline

Document Changes Record

Edit./Rev.	Date	Chapters	Reason for change
1.00	01/11/2022	All	Original Document

MEMORANDUM OF COOPERATION

Executive Summary

The purpose of this Memorandum of Cooperation is to provide the framework for the envisioned synergy (and / or cooperation) of PRECINCT and STRATEGY projects (in alphabetical order) ultimately aiming at maximising the impact of results produced as part of the research activities delivered by both consortiums. Identifying a commonality with respect to Critical Infrastructure Protection and Standardization, in their research domains, the aforementioned projects agree to proceed to a synergy along a set of specific objectives that are described subsequently.

In this respect, considering the aforementioned areas of thematical relevance between the 2 projects, the synergy outlined through the document in discussion, foresees where possible to a) leverage on lessons learned, b) extend the validation process for all results produced and c) communicate the outcomes to an extended group of potential stakeholders building up on the communities approached by both projects up to this point of their implementation. As such, this synergy will expectedly allow both projects to reach wider target audiences via suitable communication channels, fostering the active interaction with relevant parties of the first responders' / standardisation domain(s).

Provided the above, this document, having the approval and signature of the coordinators of both projects, was created with the intention of documenting and formalizing the context of all subsequent synergy activities planned to be carried out between PRECINCT and STRATEGY projects. As a starting point, a concise description of both projects is first provided followed by a brief analysis of the points this cooperation as identified at the time of signing this Memorandum of Cooperation.

- **PRECINCT Project Outline**

H2020-SU-INFRA-2020 – PRECINCT (Preparedness and Resilience Enforcement for Critical Infrastructure Cascading Cyberphysical Threats and effects with focus on district or regional protection) is an Innovation Action funded by the European Union under Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme via grant agreement no. 101021668

- SU-INFRA01-2018-2019-2020 topic: - Prevention, detection, response and mitigation of combined physical and cyber threats to critical infrastructure in Europe
- Duration: October 2021 – September 2023
- Overall budget: €9,472,739.05
- EU contribution: €7,996,658.38
- Requested funding: *funded as requested*
- Consortium: 40 partners across 12 European Countries

- Summary: PRECINCT will provide a model-driven collaborative and unifying cyber-physical security and resilience management platform for smart resilient ‘PRECINCT’s. Specifically, PRECINCT will develop the following: 1) A PRECINCT Framework Specification for systematic CIs security and resilience management fulfilling industry requirements. 2) A Cross-Facility collaborative cyber-physical Security and Resilience management Infrastructure enabling CI stakeholder communities to create AI-enabled PRECINCT Ecosystems and enhanced resilience support services. 3) A vulnerability assessment tool that uses Serious Games to identify potential vulnerabilities to cascading effects and to quantify resilience enhancement measures. 4) PRECINCT’s Digital Twins to represent the CIs network topology and metadata profiles, applying closed-loop Machine Learning techniques to detect violations and provide optimised response and mitigation measures and automated forensics. 5) Smart PRECINCT Ecosystems, deployed in four large-scale Living Labs and Transferability Validation Demonstrators, will provide measurement-based evidence of the targeted advantages and will realize Digital Twins corresponding to the CIs located therein, include active participation of emergency services and city administrations with results feeding back to the Digital Twins developments. 6) Sustainability related outputs including Capacity Building, Dissemination, Exploitation, Resilience Strategy, Policy/ Standardisation recommendations.

- **STRATEGY Project Outline**

H2020-SU-SEC-2019 – STRATEGY (Facilitating EU pre-Standardization process Through streamlining and validating interoperability in systems and procedures involved in the crisis management cycle) is an Innovation Action funded by the European Union under Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme via grant agreement no. 883520

- SU-DRS03-2019 topic: Pre-standardisation in crisis management (including natural hazard and CBRN-E emergencies)
- Duration: September 2020 – August 2023
- Overall budget: €6.833.075.00
- EU contribution: €5.997.293,25
- Requested funding: *funded as requested*
- Consortium: **23 partners** across 14 European Countries
- Summary: STRATEGY aims to contribute to the EU pre-standardization process through streamlining, testing and validating (in realistic environments) interoperability-related standardization items in systems and procedures addressing the operational needs of practitioners involved with Crisis Management across a set 8 thematic areas (1. Search and rescue, 2. Critical infrastructure protection, 3.

Response planning, 4. Command and control, 5. Early warning and Rapid damage assessment, 6. CBRN-E, 7. Training and 8. Terminology/Symbology). Currently the project is in the process of elaborating 11 Pre-Standardization Items (i.e. CEN Workshop agreements – CWAs) and 2 Technical Specification (TSs) Documents along the aforementioned thematical areas.

Joint activities and cooperation

I. OBJECTIVES

The objectives of this Memorandum of COOPERATION (MOC) between PRECINCT and STRATEGY include:

- 1) Working together, in joint activities and events towards, enhancing the extending results relevant to a) Critical Infrastructure Protection (CIP) and b) standardization and policy recommendations topics, in line to the activities specified in the PRECINCT & STRATEGY Grant Agreements respectively.

In this respect, both projects have agreed to take advantage of the validation processes being planned as part of PRECINCT, in order to encompass the validation of the pre-standardization items elaborated as part of STRATEGY in the CIP domain. More specifically the living labs that are to take place during the last quarter of PRECINCT will be investigated so as to include the validation of the CWA work on Incident situational reporting for Critical Infrastructures developed within STRATEGY. In this context the incident report structure that is addressed in the aforementioned CWA shall be incorporated in the testing environment of PRECINCT.

Specific attention shall be given to the living lab of PRECINCT that is to be held in Athens that encompasses the scenario / technical set-up the is mostly applicable to the concept of the STRATEGY CWA. This will allow investigating the applicability of the said pre-standardization item concept by an extended end-user community providing feedback & recommendations towards its completion. In addition, the end-user community of PRECINCT will expand its testing basis on interconnected CIs in line with incident reporting approaches (in a practical manner) that are in the process of being pre-standardized - ultimately enhancing the impact of its results.

- 2) Exchanging information and knowledge (non-confidential and/or sensitive). In order to ensure the full accomplishment of their pre-set research objectives and also extend the impact of produced results, both projects may be engaged in discussing / exchanging non-confidential information that falls in line to their corresponding field

of research, goals and activities. In this respect, each project may provide feedback to the approach and/or results as produced by their counterpart in this Memorandum of Cooperation. For optimally coordinating efforts in the context of the above, a series of online meetings (and face to face meetings if budget allows) will be organized for the purposes of planning, monitoring and evaluating outcomes.

- 3) To create a synergy for dissemination and communication activities, and exploit networks and contacts created as part of each project to ensure the largest / widest outreach of all results. Specific consideration shall be paid to restrictions relating to sharing of personal information and GDPR national and EU guidelines and regulations.

Indicatively as part of this synergy the following action points are being planned and could be further enhanced as optimally identified until the end of the projects in discussion.

- STRATEGY to participate in the 2nd PRECINCT Workshop planned for November 22nd 2022 in Brussels. During the event STRATEGY shall deliver a presentation of its activities and in addition participate in a round-table discussion for clarifying standardization aspects – relevant to among others CIP.
- PRECINCT shall participate in the 1st Interoperability Event organized by STRATEGY on Rome on February 15th 2023. During the event PRECINCT shall deliver examples of research activities in the CIP domain that enhance / facilitate interoperability – as relevant to the corresponding theme of STRATEGY. In addition, PRECINCT's participation during the 2nd Interoperability event shall also be assessed as per the progress status of the project close to the time of organization of the said event (approx. May 2023).
- STRATEGY shall investigate its participation to the PRECINCT could participate in events organized by STRATEGY. In this respect, organization of the 2 interoperability events were specifically mentioned for discussing interoperability-related aspects relevant to Critical Infrastructure Protection.
- Both projects will investigate the possibility of organizing a joint event approx. during the 3rd quarter of 2023.

II. POINTS OF CONTACT

The points of contact for the Memorandum of Cooperation between PRECINCT and STRATEGY will be:

PRECINCT Project Coordinator

STRATEGY Project Coordinator

Mrs. Jenny Rainbird

Mr. Giannis Chasiotis

III. DURATION OF THE AGREEMENT

This memorandum of cooperation is entered into effect.
On the 1st of November in the year 2022

This memorandum shall remain in effect until the end of each of the respective projects (listed in clause I of this document), with the possibility of further cooperations and joint activities (such as workshops, conferences and others).

Signatures:

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Name Mrs. Jenny Rainbird

Position: PRECINCT Project Coordinator

A blue ink signature is written over a blue horizontal bar, which is placed above a thin black horizontal line.

Name Mr. Giannis Chasiotis

Position: STRATEGY Project Coordinator